

eDNAqua-Plan
NEXT GENERATION OF AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY MONITORING

Report on DNA Reference Libraries

Deliverable 2.1

Work Package 2

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme, Grant Agreement No. 101112800 (eDNAqua-Plan). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Document information

Grant agreement	101112800
Project acronym	eDNAqua-Plan
Project title	A plan for a European eDNA digital ecosystem for the next generation of aquatic biodiversity monitoring
Deliverable title	Report on DNA Reference Libraries
Deliverable number	2.1.
Work package title	Audit and Gap-Analysis
Work package number	WP2
Lead beneficiary	UMinho
Author(s)	Filipe O. Costa, Jorge Moutinho, Peter Woollard, Dawid Krawczyk, Ioannis Kavakiotis, Michal Seweryn, Frédéric Rimet, Pilar Cabezas, Arne J. Beermann, Florian Leese, Spiros Papakostas, Michal Grabowski
Due date	30th Sep 2024
Submission date	30th Sep 2024
Dissemination level	Public
Type of deliverable	Report

Executive summary

This report contains an inventory of DNA barcoding projects across Europe, as well as repositories containing DNA barcode reference libraries, identifying their geographical, ecological, and taxonomic coverages. Such libraries (*sensu* Weigand et al. 2019), containing reliable and taxonomically curated DNA sequences, are essential for biodiversity monitoring, as they allow the utilisation of ecological and biogeographical information on species in a comparable manner.

The report includes a brief description of the methodologies used to perform the inventory. In order to identify DNA barcoding projects and DNA reference libraries of European aquatic biodiversity, the main approach that was followed was a survey targeting peers who are, or have been involved in relevant projects in Europe. Additionally, an experimental approach was investigated, using the development of a large language model (LLM) for automatic processing of publications' content. The collected content was explored using a list of search criteria agreed upon by the consortium members which allows for analysing gaps and overlaps of (meta)data.

The survey was intended to directly gather information from key actors in the development of DNA reference libraries of European aquatic biodiversity, increasing the likelihood of acquiring data from current projects that have yet to publish or deposit any information. Yet, its outcome is biased as it was largely dependent on the peers that responded to the survey. The experimental LLM-based approach aimed to provide an automated method for reviewing available publications, allowing for a more time-efficient data collection process. This approach also has limitations resulting from the content of the training dataset and the set of questions on which the LLM was based. Combining the two approaches facilitates a more comprehensive review of the existing libraries.

We received 49 replies but only 38, originating from 33 institutions, could be accepted for downstream analysis. Nevertheless, several replies pertained to multiple reference libraries, targeting different taxa and markers, and were considered independently whenever replies' details allowed. The majority of contributions came from academic institutions followed by governmental bodies with minimal input from stakeholders, NGOs, and a research foundation. Projects were predominantly regional in scale (34%), while international projects accounted for 28%, national projects for 23%, and local projects for 13%. DNA reference libraries of marine organisms were the most common followed by freshwater species, transitional waters, and groundwaters. Specimens were mainly sourced from captures in nature (55%), public collections (20%), and then private collections or cultures. The target taxa were primarily Eukarya, especially Metazoans (53%), with Prokaryotes (Archaea and Bacteria) accounting for 17%. Specimens were predominantly identified based on morphology (63%), while 25% using both, morphological and molecular, methods. Highly experienced identifiers (Level I; 71%) were the main contributors, focusing on species or genus level identifications (together accounting for 70% of cases). WoRMS was the main reference source for taxonomy in marine and transition waters, whereas WoRMS, along with NCBI and GBIF dominated in case of freshwaters. Most DNA reference libraries included fewer than 200 species, and the majority contained less than 500 sequenced specimens. Some projects reported sequencing between 1,000 and 3,000 specimens. Most participants (72%) reported keeping all specimens as vouchers, stored primarily in academic or museum collections, with ethanol being the commonest storage preservative, followed by sub-zero temperatures. DNA aliquots were commonly stored under sub-zero temperatures, notably at -20 °C (59%) and -80 °C (24%). A broad diversity of molecular markers was used in reference libraries for aquatic organisms. COX1 was the most targeted marker (30%), likely corresponding to sequences of the animal barcode region. The second most applied marker was mitochondrial 16S rRNA (15%), followed by the nuclear 18S rRNA (10%) and ITS (7%). The 16S rRNA and the 12S rRNA genes were also targets for bacteria and fish reference libraries. However, given that rRNA genes are lacking a standard target region (e.g. 12S, 18S, mitochondrial 16S), it is not possible to ascertain if the reference libraries correspond to the same marker region. Most projects (82%) had deposited at least some DNA reference sequences, primarily in public databases, such as BOLD and NCBI (both 41%). Metadata were deposited for 91% sequences; however, metadata

standards were not commonly followed (55% did not adhere to standards). The most frequently deposited metadata included: project identification, GPS coordinates, voucher ID and location, person collecting and identifying, and depth/altitude. Collection date was mentioned only in two cases. Deposition of specimens' images was reported in about half of the libraries. Among the sequence-associated metadata, the molecular marker and sequenced region were also frequently recorded; other elements such as PCR and sequencing primers, trace files and sequencing platforms were provided in less than half of the cases. Taxonomic curation procedures were applied in nearly 65% of the libraries, while phylogenetic congruence checks were reported in about one third of them.

From over 850 papers processed by the LLM, the most reported markers, ordered by prevalence, were COX1, 16S (no discrimination between prokaryotic and mitochondrial), ITS and 18S. Other sixteen molecular markers/regions were barely reported. A total of 55 reference databases were found in the analysed papers, of which only 20% were relevant (more than 10 reports). NCBI GenBank and SILVA were highlighted, both with ca. 38% of the reports, being followed by BOLD, UNITE, EMBL, RDP, PR2, and GreenGenes, which altogether accounted for 42%.

Regarding the repositories, a list of 25 public repositories containing DNA reference records for several molecular markers and a wide range of aquatic taxa was compiled. Twenty-one of these were qualified for the following analysis. Most of the repositories are updated periodically, but only 5 of them are updated annually. Twenty repositories cover all aquatic environments, while only four focus on marine waters and one contains only records for fresh waters. Half of the repositories store data on multiple molecular markers, with 16S rRNA data being the most abundant, followed by COI and 18S rRNA. However, 16S data pertains to two distinct markers, namely the prokaryotic and mitochondrial 16S rRNA genes. Most repositories lack detailed workflow information such as sample collection and sequence protocols. Some taxonomic curation is used by nearly all repositories but, at the same time, most lack confidence levels for taxonomic identifications. Most repositories have a standardised structure, but they usually do not offer API, desktop or console support. Four repositories lack web interfaces. FASTA is the most common format in which the data can be downloaded from the databases.

In conclusion, while a reasonable progress has been made in Europe to build reference libraries for aquatic organisms, there is a considerable dispersion of initiatives and uncoordinated efforts. This resulted in reference libraries with varied levels of comprehensiveness, metadata content, taxonomic curation, auditability, accessibility and interoperability. Hence, there is a strong need for standardized metadata practices, rigorous and harmonized full-curation procedures, and improved data-sharing mechanisms. Results from this report will help to identify the major deficiencies in content and format of reference library data, thereby contributing to design broadly applicable recommendations to improve data quality and adherence to FAIR principles. Enhancing these aspects will be essential for advancing biodiversity monitoring and research efforts across European aquatic ecosystems.

Table of contents

Executive summary	2
Table of contents	4
Abbreviations and acronyms	6
1. Introduction	7
2. Methodology	8
2.A. Survey.....	8
2.A.1. Questionnaire development	8
2.A.2. Questionnaire distribution	8
2.A.3. Raised problems	9
2.B. DNA barcode reference libraries survey	10
2.B.1. Required metadata properties.....	10
2.B.2. Assessment of DNA barcode reference libraries	12
2.B.3. Large Language Model (LLM).....	14
2.C. Data analysis	15
3. Results	16
3.A. Survey results	16
3.A.1. Overview	16
3.A.2. Projects' ranges and targeted environments.....	18
3.A.3. Sources of specimens and target taxa.....	18
3.A.4. Number of species and specimens used for building DNA reference libraries	22
3.A.5. Vouchers	24
3.A.6. DNA aliquot from reference specimen	26
3.A.7. Molecular markers.....	28
3.A.8. DNA reference sequences depositing.....	28
3.A.9. Generated metadata	30
3.A.10. DNA reference library management.....	32
3.B. Databases review	34
3.B.1. Databases characterisation.....	34
3.B.2. Molecular markers.....	35
3.B.3. Metadata	38
3.B.4. Taxonomic identification and curation.....	39
3.B.5. Database accessibility.....	40
3.B.6. Upload and download of data and metadata	41
3.C. Large Language Model (LLM)	45
3.C.1. Molecular markers	45
3.C.2. Reference databases.....	45
4. Discussion and Conclusions	47
4.A. Scope of survey's results	47
4.B. Specimen source, taxonomic identification and processing	47
4.C. DNA sequence data, metadata and data management.....	48
4.E. Databases review	49
4.F. Final conclusions.....	50
5. References	51

Contributions	52
Appendix (Supplementary Material)	53
Appendix 1. Questionnaire structure	53
Appendix 2. Classification system for the accuracy of specimen’s taxonomic identification.....	57
Appendix 3. DNA reference databases review (manual).....	57
Appendix 4. Dataset developed for retraining Llama2.....	57
Appendix 5. Questionnaire resulting data.....	57
Appendix 6. Target taxa	57

Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
BIOPOLIS	Associação Biopolis
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
DMP	Data Management Plan
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
EC	European Commission
ECB	European Central Bank
eDNA	Environmental DNA
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
EMBRC-ERIC	European Marine Biological Resource Centre - European Research Infrastructure Consortium
EU	European Union
EV ILVO	Eigen Vermogen Van Het Instituut Voor Landbouw - En Visserijonderzoek
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GA	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IAB	International Advisory Board
IHU	Diethens Panepistimio Ellados
INRAE	Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement
LifeWatch-ERIC	E-Science European Infrastructure for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research - European Research Infrastructure Consortium
NIVA	Norsk Institutt for Vannforskning
PIC	Project Implementation Committee
PMG	Project Management Guide
PMT	Project Management Team
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprise(s)
SSBE	Seascape Belgium
SU	Sorbonne Université
SYKE	Suomen ympäristökeskus / Finnish Environment Institute
UDE	Universitaet Duisburg-Essen
ULOD	Uniwersytet Lodzki
UMINHO	Universidade do Minho
UNESCO	United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organisation
UEG	Universitat de Valencia
VAT	Value Added Tax
VLIZ	Vlaams Instituut Voor de Zee
WP	Work Package(s)
WU	Wageningen University

1. Introduction

I. eDNAqua-Plan project description and aims

The fundamental aim of the eDNAqua-Plan project is to promote synergies, harmonisation, and interoperability between existing EU initiatives and resources linked to the generation, storage, analysis, and accessibility of DNA (meta)barcoding data, with an emphasis on environmental DNA (eDNA) data from marine and freshwater ecosystems. As a result, the project will provide a framework to maximise the efficiency of forthcoming aquatic biodiversity monitoring activities. The project consortium fulfils these goals by the following subsequent steps:

- Conducting a comprehensive review of the current landscape of DNA barcoding and eDNA-based monitoring initiatives and projects as well as their analysis workflows.
- Comparing and mapping the data standards across DNA barcode reference libraries and (e)DNA data repositories to identify possible linkages across data types and to highlight remaining gaps in this digital ecosystem.
- Providing operational input and testing the results of the above inventories using a wide selection of existing eDNA-based marine and freshwater monitoring projects in Europe.
- Delivering an operational blueprint, a strategic vision and roadmap, as well as viable options towards the sustainability of a future aquatic (e)DNA digital ecosystem for Europe.

II. Framing of the WP2 aims within the eDNAqua-Plan project

WP2 is a critical component of the project, as it provides other WPs with actual data on the current landscape of DNA barcoding and eDNA-based initiatives and projects. This data serves as a solid foundation for the comparative critical assessment of the effectiveness of current workflows and, subsequently, for proposing best practices and identifying areas of improvement.

III. WP2.1 objectives description

The objectives of WP2.1 are to identify regional, national, and international DNA barcoding projects and initiatives in Europe and to provide taxonomic, geographical, and a (meta)data overlap/gap analysis for DNA barcode reference libraries.

2. Methodology

In order to identify projects that are building DNA barcode reference libraries for European aquatic biodiversity, two approaches were followed: i) a survey targeting peers who are or have been involved in projects in the investigated area, developed by the manual search team (UMinho); and ii) the development of LLM for automatic processing of the publications' content, developed by the bioinformatics team (ULod). The former approach aimed to directly gather information from key actors involved in developing DNA barcode reference libraries for European aquatic biodiversity, increasing the likelihood of collecting data from ongoing projects that are not yet publicly available. The latter approach provided an automatic way to review available publications, allowing for a more time-efficient information collection process. By combining the two approaches, we were able to obtain a comprehensive review of the existing DNA barcode reference libraries.

2.A. Survey

2.A.1. Questionnaire development

The survey's questionnaire was developed by the manual research team, with significant input from WP2 members to ensure it met the project's aims, while remaining concise and easy to answer. Overall, the questionnaire included 45 questions covering various aspects, such as project identification, targeted biodiversity (taxa, ecosystems), specimen sources, specimen identification, storage of both voucher and DNA aliquots, molecular markers used, deposited sequences and respective databases, as well as generated metadata and its deposition/storage. Additionally, questions regarding DNA reference library management were included, such as reference barcode validation procedures, taxonomy curation procedures of the DNA barcode reference library, maintenance of previous versions of curation, and tracking of experts curating the DNA reference libraries. Structurally, the questionnaire consisted of three main components: i) basic questions regarding the contributors' identification; ii) general questions regarding barcode generation; and iii) questions regarding DNA reference management. For more details on the questionnaire structure, see Appendix 1.

The questionnaire was created in two different formats. The first format was a spreadsheet file, designed to systematically collect answers from individuals involved in multiple projects, with each row corresponding to a different project and columns corresponding to various questions about each project. Respondents were expected to download the spreadsheet, provide their answers in the respective cells, and to then send the completed spreadsheet file via email to a specified email address. The second format was an online Google Forms questionnaire, accessed via a link sent to all recipients. This format aimed to provide a more user-friendly and appealing way to quickly and easily submit answers. The same email address that was mentioned above was also used to handle any queries regarding the questionnaire. Overall, the questions and structure were consistent across both formats, with only minor format adaptations, and the recipients were free to choose how to submit their responses.

Specifically for a question about the level of expertise of taxonomic identifiers, we adopted the classification system described in Ward (2012) that considers a 5-level grade of expertise (available in Appendix 2), and provided this information to respondents.

2.A.2. Questionnaire distribution

Once finalised, and with the agreement of all WP2 members, the questionnaire was shared with eDNAqua-Plan members and other networks on February 14, 2024. Project members were encouraged to further distribute the questionnaire within their own contacts and networks. Initially, the survey was set to remain open for one month, but due to lower-than-expected participation, the deadline was extended by two weeks. Despite these extensions, participation remained insufficient, prompting a mass email to approximately 290 researchers on March 24, 2024. These researchers were known contributors to the DNA barcoding and/or building DNA reference libraries for European aquatic biodiversity.

Ultimately, the questionnaire remained open for three and a half months, closing on May 22, 2024 (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Cumulative and daily number of replies, along the whole period during which the survey form remained open.

2.A.3. Raised problems

I. Questionnaire design

We acknowledge that the design of the questionnaire may have hindered its effectiveness. The development of two formats did not yield the expected results, as several contributors with multiple projects responded only using the Google Forms format. Moreover, the questionnaire was considerably extensive, which might have been too demanding for individuals with multiple projects and diverse research backgrounds, leading to ‘stakeholder fatigue’. Although the Google Forms format was developed with a simpler structure to reduce the time required, it may not have fully compensated for the above-mentioned challenges associated with the spreadsheet format.

II. Questionnaire distribution

Although there was a consensus within WP2 regarding the acceptable coverage of the survey, we recognise that there may have been room for improvement, to increase public engagement and broader representation. The questionnaire was initially distributed via email to major European barcoding/genomic networks, such as iBOL Europe (formerly known as BIOSCAN Europe), and BGE (Biodiversity Genomics Europe), but project members were also strongly encouraged to share the questionnaire within their own networks and contacts. However, the number of contributions was lower than expected. Hence, upon an extensive review of 2,551 publications, compiled from Web of Science (including topics on DNA barcoding, eDNA metabarcoding, Europe(an), and aquatic biodiversity) and additional sources from manual research, was conducted. As a result, a list of approximately 290 potential recipients was compiled. These recipients were contacted via email to further distribute the questionnaire. Some of them admitted they have not previously heard of the survey, revealing that the initial distribution approach was insufficient. Hence, this secondary approach aimed to broaden the range of contacts to increase the pool of potential contributors.

Despite these efforts, the number of responses remained low: we received replies from only five individuals (1.7% out of the 290 contacted). We suspect that sending the email simultaneously to a large number of contacts may have contributed to the low response rate. For instance, approximately 6.2% of the email addresses were found to be inactive, and around 1.7% were either blocked or the email was rejected. Additionally, it is likely that several emails were flagged as spam, although such information is unattainable.

2.B. DNA barcode reference libraries survey

2.B.1. Required metadata properties

Under the scope of the M2.1, a list of agreed search criteria (metadata components) to provide taxonomic, geographical, ecological and (meta)data overlap/gap analysis for the DNA barcode reference libraries, was finalised in November 2023. This was achieved through a series of online meetings and email discussions among the leaders and members of tasks within the WP2 and WP3 (Table 1).

Table 1. List of the agreed search criteria under the scope of the M2.1, by project members from WP2 and WP3.

No.	Name	Type	Description	Values
1	data_metadata_link\	string	Explanation about how the data (sequences) are linked with its metadata. Tells if there are separate entities within the database or they are the same thing.	free text
2	record_URL	boolean	Information if there is a URL or URI to the source data records. This will be specified during data analysis.	true/false
3	metadata_record_URL	boolean	Information if there is a URL or URI or another type of link that indicates the place where metadata is stored. This will be specified during data analysis.	true/false
4	paper_DOI_number	boolean	Information if there is a DOI identifier for the paper which "delivers" the data and describes them. This will be specified during data analysis.	true/false
5	paper_link	boolean	Information if there is a URL or URI to the paper which "delivers" the data and describes them. This will be specified during data analysis.	true/false
6	DB_name	string	Official name of the database where the data is stored.	free text
7	DB_use_index	integer	Information of how often researchers are using this database estimated by analysing papers. Expressed using the percentage of publications where the database name appears.	from 0 to 100
8	DB_using community	string	Explains if the database stores marine water data or freshwater data. Estimated by analysing papers that used the database.	"only fresh water", "mostly fresh water", "mixed", "mostly marine water", "only marine water"
9	number of records	integer	Total count of records in database.	integer numbers above 0
10	web_interface	boolean	Tells whether the database has an interactive web interface enabling browsing and downloading available data.	true/false
11	API	boolean	Tells whether the database has API (Application Programming Interface) enabling browsing and downloading available data.	true/false
12	application	boolean	Tells whether the database supports any desktop or console application enabling browsing and downloading available data.	true/false

No.	Name	Type	Description	Values
13	GPS_coordinates_available	boolean	Tells whether the database contains information about GPS coordinates for samples.	true/false
14	data_export_format	string	Information about the data file formats available for download.	list of available formats
15	metadata_export_format	string	Information about the metadata file formats available for download.	list of available formats
16	env_data_contains	boolean	Tells whether the database contains the environmental samples data.	true/false
17	barcode_taxonomy_confidence	boolean	Tells whether the database has information about the confidence level of the barcode and taxonomy linkage.	true/false
18	annually_updated	boolean	Tells whether the database is updated every year.	true/false
19	data_paper_location	string	Information about where is the data available: main paper or supplement.	"main","supplement"
20	sequences_processed	string	Tells whether the sequences in the database are raw or processed.	"raw","processed","both"
21	DB_standard_consistent	boolean	Tells whether the database structure is consistent	true/false
22	DB_mandatory_metadata	string	Lists metadata attributes that are necessary for the database.	list of attributes names
23	data_file_format	string	Lists the sequencing data file format the database supports on upload.	list of supported formats
24	metadata_file_format	string	Lists the metadata file format the database supports on upload.	list of supported formats
25	metadata_file_schema	string	Tells what is the metadata file scheme.	free text
26	DB_active	boolean	Tells whether new records are being added to the database.	true/false
27	DB_curation	boolean	Tells whether there is any curation of the data in the database.	true/false
28	sample_collection	boolean	Tells if there is information of sample collection method. This will be specified during data analysis.	true/false
29	DNA_extraction	boolean	Tells if there is information of DNA extraction method. This will be specified during data analysis.	true/false
30	sequence_methodology	boolean	Tells if there is information of URL to the sequence protocol in protocol.io. This will be specified during data analysis.	true/false
31	sequencing_strategy	boolean	Tells if there is information of the overall sequencing strategy used in the experiment. This will be specified during data analysis.	true/false
32	analysis_workflow	boolean	Tells if there is information on the sequence analysis workflow. This will be specified during data analysis.	true/false
33	directly_uploaded	boolean	Tells whether the record was uploaded directly to the database or it was mined from another database.	true/false
34	barcode_name	string	List of barcodes using which the supplied data is sequenced.	list of barcodes names or "private"

No.	Name	Type	Description	Values
35	barcode_certain	boolean	Tells if the database is doing a comparison of a barcode for certainty.	true/false
36	taxonomy_origin	string	Tells what is the reference database name used for the data taxonomical identification.	free text
37	taxonomy_URL	string	URL or URI of the reference database used for the data taxonomical identification.	HTTPS link
38	taxonomically_identified	boolean	Tells whether there is taxonomical identification in the database.	true/false
39	taxonomical_name	boolean	Tells whether there is a taxonomic name for the sequences in the database.	true/false
40	taxonomy_linking	boolean	Tells whether there is any linking method that refers to some of the "big" databases e.g. after clicking in web interface.	true/false

2.B.2. Assessment of DNA barcode reference libraries

Upon consultation with WP2 members, a list of the 25 most relevant DNA reference databases was compiled (Table 2) and values determined for 40 search criteria (metadata components) using mainly manual inspection by bioinformaticians. A spreadsheet was created, with metadata properties as rows and repositories as columns. The spreadsheets were then combined, and the nomenclature was harmonised to generate a single, unified spreadsheet (version 1.0). Although compiled, four databases were not considered for further analysis. MARES consists of a pipeline developed in order to aid the development of more updated and/or taxa-specific DNA reference libraries, based on NCBI GenBank's and BOLD's records, hence not being a database per se. mkCOLnr encompassed the overall data as COLnr, but with additional scripts (Table 2), hence it can be considered as the same COLnr which was herein reviewed. The list of the compiled databases is represented in Table 2. Additionally, it was not possible to get information on RDP and PhytoRef. For further details on data regarding manual review of the DNA reference databases, see Appendix 3.

Table 2. List of databases containing DNA reference records, compiled according to the eDNAqua-Plan project members' knowledge. Underlined databases were not included in the analysis.

Database	URL	Description	Activity
COLnr	https://zenodo.org/records/6555985	Downloadable database, featuring COX1 sequences extracted from NCBI-nt and BOLD. Not limited to a taxon	One-time snapshot
NISdb	https://github.com/jesuszarcero/NISdb	Downloadable database/repository with COX1-5P sequences from NIS that spread to Western Mediterranean region	One-time snapshot
DUFA	https://github.com/uit-metabarcoding/DUFA	Downloadable database with COX1 and 12S rRNA of fish	One-time snapshot
GSR	https://manichanh.vhir.org/gsrdb/	Downloadable database, that features an integrated and manually curated database for bacterial and archaeal 16S rRNA	NA

Database	URL	Description	Activity
EUKRibo	https://zenodo.org/records/6896896	Downloadable database, that features manually curated 18S rDNA eukaryotic sequences	One-time snapshot
MIMt	https://mimt.bu.biopolis.pt/	Downloadable database featuring 16S rRNA sequences of bacteria and archaea	Maintained
Metabarpark	https://github.com/metabarpark/Reference-databases	Downloadable database focusing in COX1 and 18S rRNA reference sequences of marine benthic communities	One-time snapshot
BOLD Systems	https://boldsystems.org/	Cloud-based data storage and analysis platform. Features DNA sequences from several molecular markers of Eukaryotes, focus on COX1 and animals	Maintained
SILVA	https://www.arb-silva.de/	Cloud-based data storage and analysis platform. Features DNA sequences from small and large subunits ribosomal RNA for all life domains	Maintained
UNITE	https://unite.ut.ee/	Cloud-based data storage and management platform. It is centred in eukaryotic nuclear ribosomal ITS region sequences	Maintained
MIDORI	https://www.reference-midori.info/	Downloadable database. Features sequences from eukaryotic mitochondrial DNA	Maintained (recent)
PR2	https://pr2-database.org/	Cloud-based data storage that features three interconnected 18S rRNA databases, focusing on protists	Maintained
Open Tree of life Taxonomy (OTT)	https://tree.opentreeoflife.org/about/taxonomy-version/ott3.6	Cloud-based repository of phylogenetic data	Maintained
MycDiversity DataBase (MDD)	https://mycodiversity.liacs.nl/	Curated database of public integrated samples and barcodes (ITS)	Maintained
GreenGenes2	https://greengenes2.ucsd.edu/ https://greengenes.lbl.gov/Download/	Downloadable database focused on both archeal and bacterial 16S rRNA	Maintained
µgreen	http://microgreen-23sdatabase.ea.inra.fr/	Downloadable database focused on photosynthetic eukaryotic microalgae and prokaryotic cyanobacteria (23S rRNA)	One-time snapshot
Diat.barcode	https://cartel-collection.hub.inrae.fr/barcoding-databases/diat.barcode	Downloadable reference library specific for diatoms, based on rbcL, 18S, 28S rRNA, COX1, and ITS	One-time snapshot

Database	URL	Description	Activity
Phytool	https://github-carrtel.shinyapps.io/phytool_v2/	Downloadable database of curated barcodes of microalgae, focused on 16S, 18S, 23S rRNA and rbcL	One-time snapshot
GTDB	https://gtdb.ecogenomic.org/	Downloadable database featuring microbial genomes	Maintained
MZGdb	https://metazoogene.org/database/	Downloadable database focused in marine zooplankton DNA reference sequences of COX1, 18S, 16S, 12S, and 28S rRNA	Maintained
FWAlgaeDB	http://www.fwalagedb.com/#/home	Downloadable database featuring freshwater algae genomes	Maintained (recent)
mkCOInr	https://github.com/meglecz/mkCOInr	Similar content as COInr, but with additional scripts	One-time snapshot
PhytoRef	phytoref.sb-roscoff.fr/	Downloadable reference database featuring the plastidial 16S rRNA of photosynthetic eukaryotes	NA
MARES	https://github.com/wpearman1996/MARES_database_pipeline	Script that allows to followed the authors methodology to generate a DNA reference libraries	One-time snapshot
RDP	https://rncentral.org/expert-database/rdp	Downloadable database featuring bacterial and archaeal SSU rRNA sequences and fungal LSU rRNA	Maintained

2.B.3. Large Language Model (LLM)

In this section, we provide a short overview on how the content of scientific publications was explored and analysed to extract information for both the M2.1 (molecular markers used, DNA barcode reference library used for taxonomic identification) and M2.2 (e.g., the sampling strategy, DNA extraction protocol sourced from protocols.io, sequencing strategy, the sequencing analysis workflow, and data storage). For this purpose, the manual processing team built a training set of 117 publications, available at Appendix 4. The preparation of the training set involved identifying relevant publications from the field of biology and answering a series of questions regarding the analysed publications. The dataset was then used to retrain the Llama2 language model from Meta Inc (Touvron et al. 2023).

A system consisting of web crawlers was produced to automatically download the content of publications from PubMed and PubMed Central. Subsequently, the content from the Materials and Methods sections of the analysed publications was sent to the Llama2 language model, which answered the same questions as the experts in the manual processing approach. The first question was whether a given publication describes a study analysed eDNA. If the publication was not classified as analysing eDNA, further analyses were rejected. The language model generated false positives when samples collected from the environment were then cultured using cell lines, hence additional verification was applied by asking the model whether this was the case. The data obtained from all these processes were saved into a MongoDB database.

The process of data mining from publications was also carried out using the Llama2 model. The series of answers to each question was fed back into the language model, which was then asked to summarise the information provided and calculate statistics. Further analysis of the results was done manually.

The full database of information gathered from scientific papers is available at Appendix 5. The Python code is posted in this [link](#).

2.C. Data analysis

As previously mentioned in section 2.A.3., the questionnaire was developed in two structurally different formats, namely Google Forms and a spreadsheet. Considering the required effort to complete each survey format, the former was found to be more appealing to the majority of the contributors (more details in section 3.A.1.). However, the Google Forms format was too simplistic, particularly for cases in which further comprehensive input was required. These cases usually involved individuals with multiple projects (either similar or different from each other), or single projects where further details: e.g., when multiple different taxa, and/or multiple environment types (freshwater, marine, transitional, and groundwater) were involved, and/or when the project range was broad. Hence, the analysis presented here was developed following a conservative approach, although with room for presumptions. For instance, several respondents stated to not keep all specimens as vouchers, but some of those further provided information in the following questions (e.g., voucher material kept, where and how it was stored), which inferred that these individuals were keeping at least some of the specimens as vouchers. Additionally, the available data was not systematically and comprehensively formatted (Google Forms) in order to assess each single project or DNA reference library's employed approaches, however it provided a view of the methodology and targets of several relevant contributors in generating DNA reference sequences for European aquatic taxa. For further details on the dataset structure see Appendix 6. On the other hand, DNA reference databases review depicted a more comprehensive approach which allowed a more detailed profiling, across several considered variables (see Table 2), of each database.

All analyses and data visualisation was performed in the RStudio environment (version 4.3.3; R Core Team, 2024; Posit Team, 2024). Due to the nature of both the survey and database review data, the analysis generally encompassed qualitative analysis, with no statistical analysis included. Answering institutions mapping was developed using the *ggmap* function from the package of the same name (Kahle and Wickham, 2013) to visually represent the amount of answering institutions per country. Additionally, a *treemap* was developed using the *treemap* function from the package of the same name (Tennekes, 2023) to represent the great diversity of molecular markers and its proportional reported cases. Following, *ggplot2* package (Wickham, 2016) was used to visually represent quantitative data and plotting contributing institutions along with *ggmap*.

3. Results

3.A. Survey results

3.A.1. Overview

Highlights:

- We received 49 replies from 45 respondents, of which 86.7% were submitted via Google Forms, and 76.7% were accepted for analysis.
- The analysis only included 38 of the replies, representing 33 institutions, but several replies pertained to multiple reference libraries, targeting different taxa and markers, and were considered independently whenever replies' details allowed. Most of the accepted contributions came from academic institutions (74.4%), followed by governmental bodies (17.9%), with minimal input from stakeholders, NGOs, and a research foundation.

The questionnaire yielded a total of 49 replies (Figure 1) from 45 respondents, representing 39 institutions. Nearly 87% of the respondents submitted their input via Google Forms, leading to higher redundancy. Several instances of multiple answers from the same respondent occurred, either reflecting different projects or containing similar inputs. While the former cases were accepted, the latter were addressed by contacting contributors for clarification. If contact was not possible, the differences between answers were assessed and merged where feasible. Additionally, some participants were contacted to clarify overly general answers, overlooked questions, and to address omitted sections of the questionnaire, especially when it was inferred they had contributed to both types of projects, but answered only the first part of the survey.

According to the project's guidelines, a fraction of the responses could not be accepted. Specifically, only responses from institutions with projects fully or partially developed within the European territory (general project description) were considered, regardless of the participant's affiliation. Consequently, 76.7% of the Google Forms contributions and all contributions to the spreadsheet format were accepted (for further details see Appendix 6). The majority of the represented institutions were European, with a small fraction of accepted responses from non-European institutions ($n = 3$, from Israel, Saudi Arabia, and Mexico, see Table 3; Figure 2). In total, submissions from 38 contributors representing 33 institutions listed in Table 3 were included for further analysis. Major contributions originated from academic institutions (74.4%), followed by governmental institutions (17.9%). Only a single stakeholder remained in the final dataset, along with one non-governmental organisation (NGO), and one research foundation (Table 3).

Table 3. List of represented institutions according to accepted contributions from the DNA reference libraries survey (both formats). Non-European institutions with acceptable replies are underlined.

Country	Institutions	Acronym	Type of Institutions	No. of replies
Austria	University of Innsbruck	UIBK	Academic	1
Finland	Finnish Environment Institute	SYKE	Governmental	1
France	Roscoff Biological Station/Sorbonne University	CRNS-SU	Academic	1
	National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment	INRAE	Governmental	2
	Research Institute for Development	IRD	Academic	1
	PatriNat	-	Academic	1
	Tara Ocean Foundation	TOF	Non-Governmental Organisation	1
Georgia	Ilia State University	ISU	Academic	1
Germany	Biome-id	-	Stakeholder	1
	University of Duisburg-Essen	UDE	Academic	2

Country	Institutions	Acronym	Type of Institutions	No. of replies
Greece	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	AUTH	Academic	1
Italy	Anton Dohrn Biologic Station	SZN	Governmental	1
	University of Bologna	UniBo	Academic	1
	University of Milano-Bicocca	UNIMI	Academic	1
Lithuania	Nature Research Centre	NRC	Governmental	1
Malta	University of Malta	UM	Academic	1
Netherlands	Naturalis Biodiversity Centre	NBC	Academic	1
	Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research	NIOZ	Research Foundation	1
Norway	Norwegian University of Science and Technology	NTNU	Academic	2
	University of Bergen	UiB	Academic	1
Poland	University of Lodz	UniLodz	Academic	2
Portugal	Research Centre in Biodiversity and Genetic Resources (Porto)	CIBIO-Porto	Academic	2
	University of Minho	UM	Academic	1
Slovakia	Comenius University in Bratislava	UNIBA	Academic	1
Spain	AZTI	-	Academic	1
	University of Santiago de Compostela	USC	Academic	1
Sweden	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences	SLU	Academic	1
	University of Gothenburg	UGOT	Academic	1
Turkey	Institute of Marine Sciences - Middle East Technical University	IMS-METU	Academic	1
Israel	Hebrew University of Jerusalem	HUJI	Academic	1
	Israel Oceanographic and Limnological Research Institute	IORL	Governmental	2
Mexico	El Colegio de la Frontera Sur	ECOSUR	Academic	1
Saudi Arabia	King Abdullah University of Science and Technology	KAUST	Academic	1

Figure 2. Country distribution of the institutions that replied to the DNA reference barcode library survey. The number of institutions per country is represented by a colour grading from yellow (lowest, n = 1) to

red (highest, n = 5). Countries of which no institutions replied to the survey, or their input was not accepted, are represented in grey.

3.A.2. Projects' ranges and targeted environments

Highlights:

- Regional-scale projects as a whole dominated in replies (34%), though international projects comprised of ca. 28% alone, while national and local projects represented 23% and 13% of the cases, respectively.
- DNA reference libraries of marine organisms were the most common (42%), followed by those occupying fresh (33.3% - one third), transitional waters (15%) and groundwaters (5%).

A great diversity of project range was found, though regional-scaled projects were found to be predominant in aquatic biodiversity, with approximately 34% cases referring to it (Figure 3A). However, regional-scaled projects were here considered as two sub-categories, namely, regional-sized within national borders (ca. 18%) or beyond two or more countries (international; ca. 16%). The former, generally encompasses reasonable-sized areas within a country, though not taking the full country's area, while the latter encompasses regions across several countries, following similar characteristics. International and national-sized projects include cases which targeted full-scale countries (several or single, respectively), which both represented approximately 28% and 23%, respectively. More locally focused projects represented approximately 13% of the cases. One submission did not indicate the scale of the developed project.

DNA reference libraries of marine organisms were the most frequently reported in the submitted answers, corresponding to approximately 42% of the cases, followed by those for freshwater (ca. 33.3%) and transitional water organisms (15%) (Figure 3B). Only three cases involved DNA reference libraries for groundwater species. In one case, the environment type encompassed in the contributor's project was not specified. Additionally, two terrestrial cases were included. Although these did not meet the eDNAqua-Plan project's criteria (aquatic species), they could not be excluded due to the nature of the Google Forms submissions. The form was not designed to gather information on multiple projects, especially if they were very divergent, making it challenging to distinguish and filter out non-aquatic data. Despite their inclusion, these cases are expected to have a negligible impact on the downstream analysis and were thus not considered as a variable of interest.

Figure 3. Total cases reporting projects' geographical range according to the submitted answers (A) and the targeted aquatic environment types.

3.A.3. Sources of specimens and target taxa

Highlights:

- **Specimen source:** 55% of the cases reported using specimens captured in nature, followed by public collections (20%), and then private collections and cultures (a similar number of cases).

- **Target taxa:** Eukarya was the most represented from acquired survey data, with ca. 83% of the cases reporting. Prokaryotes (Archaea and Bacteria) accounted for ca. 17%. Metazoan were the most reported eukaryotic taxa (53%).
- **Specimen source and identification:** Most specimens were primarily identified by morphology (ca. 63%). Simultaneous employment of morphological and molecular identification still depicted a considerable representation with one fourth of the cases.
- **Identifier expertise and level of identification:** Highly experienced identifiers (Level I; ca. 71%) were the main contributors to taxa identification across all environments. Specimens were predominantly identified to the species or genus level in most cases (together accounted for approximately 70% of the reported cases), regardless of the taxonomic group. Though such may have been biased according to the most targeted taxonomic groups which the contributing projects reported.
- **Cross-reference source:** WoRMS was the primary taxonomic source used, with approximately 24% of the cases. GBIF and NCBI taxonomy were also notable.

Specimen source

Overall, specimens collected in nature have been the most frequently used source for developing DNA reference libraries, regardless of the environment in which the specimens occur (Table 4). Approximately 55% of cases were found to report the use of specimens captured from their natural habitats across all environment types. Specimens from public collections (such as museums) also depicted a considerable representation, with around 20% of the cases reporting it. Private collections (personal) and cultures-originated specimens were reported by a similar amount of cases (see Table 4). Such an overall pattern was found throughout all analysed environment types.

Table 4. Source of specimens for building DNA reference libraries of European aquatic species biodiversity according to the submitted answers.

Specimen origin	No. of cases (n total = 64)			
	Freshwater	Marine	Transitional	Total
Nature	18	23	8	35
Cultures	3	7	3	7
Public collections	7	11	5	13
Private collections	4	5	2	8
No answer	1	-	-	1

Target taxa

The majority of the survey inputs represented eukaryotes (ca. 83%), among which metazoans constituted the bulk, comprising nearly 67% of the reported libraries (Figure 4). Prokaryotic libraries accounted for around 17%, among which Archaea and Bacteria were similarly represented. Non-metazoan eukaryotes reported included Chromista and plants (ca. 16% and 3%, respectively). Invertebrates contributed to the majority of the metazoan reports (ca. 53%), while vertebrates (majority represented by fish libraries) accounted for only approximately 15%.

Several generalist terms were used to describe the targeted taxa. For instance, “Plankton” was used to designate simultaneously Bacteria and Archaea (mentioned as Prokaryotes), Eukarya, and Virus. These groups were here considered individually but in order cases it was not possible to discriminate further since no further details were given (e.g., Eukarya and microalgae). Metazoa, Chromista, Plantae were the only ones that provided further discrimination on the targeted taxa (see Appendix 7).

Figure 4. Number of libraries reported for major organismal groups per type of environment type (A), and proportion of major metazoan taxa reported per environment type (B).

Taxonomic identification of specimen, identifier expertise and level of identification of the specimen

Specimens were primarily identified based on morphology, regardless of the sampled environment (ca. 63%; see Table 5). Still, a considerable number of reports indicated the simultaneous use of both morphological and molecular identification methods, accounting for one fourth of the cases. Overall, there were very few cases where only molecular methods were used for taxonomic identification. In fact, none were reported for transitional waters, while two cases were noted for marine and one for freshwater organisms. The latter involved the identification of macroinvertebrates, whereas the former encompassed small-sized organisms such as microalgae and plankton (encompassing Bacteria, Archaea, Virus and microeukarya), as well as Archaea and Bacteria. In one case, the method of taxonomic identification was not specified.

Table 5. Methods of taxonomic identification of specimens used for building DNA reference libraries of European aquatic biodiversity.

Specimen Identification Method	No. of cases (n total = 40)			
	Freshwater	Marine	Transitional	Total
Morphology	14	16	5	25
Molecular	1	2	-	3
Both	4	6	2	10
No answer	2	2	2	2

As expected, metazoans were predominantly reported for each specimen identification method, except molecular methods. Diatoms, however, displayed an opposite trend, particularly in marine and transitional waters, where they were exclusively identified using both approaches. For freshwater specimens, while some were identified using both methods, most cases reported morphological identification.

Highly experienced taxonomy identifiers (Level I) were the primary contributors to taxa identification in the reported cases of DNA reference libraries for European biodiversity (ca. 71%),

indicating reliable identifications. However, a range of identification expertise was evident (Table 6). The classification system for taxonomic identifiers used here was adapted from Ward's (2012) system for evaluating the reliability of identifications. For further detailed information on the system of classification used, see Appendix 2. Level II identifiers' expertise scarcely followed, with approximately 18% of the cases reporting it. Less experienced identifiers vaguely reported, with one and two cases of Level V and IV, respectively. Although all cases accounted for projects that employed both morphological and molecular identification, with an exception with a single project, which was morphology-based. A single response did not provide usable information about the identifier's level of expertise.

Table 6. Classification of the level of expertise of the identifiers involved in the morphological identification of specimens, according to the questionnaire's submitted answers.

Level of expertise	No. of cases (n total = 34)			
	Freshwater	Marine	Transitional	Total
I	13	16	6	24
II	2	4	-	6
III	-	-	-	-
IV	2	-	-	2
V	1	-	1	1
Unusable	-	1	-	1

Specimens were typically identified to the species or genus level in the majority of cases, irrespective of the taxonomic group or targeted environment (Table 7). Indeed, both accounted for approximately 70% of the reported cases. Family-level identifications also accounted for a significant number of reports (n = 12). Additional taxon-specific levels of identification were further reported, specifically, subclades, subclusters and ecotypes were reported once each for Bacteria. Subspecies and subfamily identifications were also reported once each for metazoans. However, such results may have been biased based on the projects' targeted taxonomic groups that responded to the survey (see Figure 4).

Table 7. Level of identification typically targeted during morphological identification of specimens, prior to sequence generation and molecular characterisation. (*) Encompassed identification levels that are less specific, most representative of subgroups of major taxonomic levels, such as subfamily, subspecies, subclades, subclusters, and ecotypes.

Taxonomic level of identification	No. of cases (n total = 81)			
	Freshwater	Marine	Transitional	Total
Phylum	1	1	1	2
Class	1	1	1	2
Order	3	1	1	4
Family	6	7	3	12

Taxonomic level of identification	No. of cases (n total = 81)			
	Freshwater	Marine	Transitional	Total
Genus	11	15	6	22
Species	18	24	9	35
Other*	1	2	-	3
No answer	1	1	-	1

Cross-reference source

The sources used for cross-referencing specimen's taxonomy varied according to the environment from which the specimens originated. While some sources held similar importance across different environments, notable differences were observed. For instance, the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS, <https://www.marinespecies.org/>), emerged as the main source for cross-referencing specimens' identifications, even for freshwater cases (overall ca. 24%). However, in freshwater environments, WoRMS was used as frequently as the GBIF (Global Biodiversity Information Facility, <https://www.gbif.org/>) (n = 8), but NCBI Taxonomy (National Center for Biotechnology Information, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) was the most reported (see Table 8). Beyond online platforms, several also reported the use of literature or consulting with more experienced peers, although for a much less number of cases.

Table 8. List of reported sources used for cross-referencing taxonomic identifications of specimens for building DNA reference libraries of European aquatic biodiversity. "Unknown" values encompass questionnaire submissions that did not provide any or acceptable information.

Cross Reference Source	No. of cases (n total = 86)			
	Freshwater	Marine	Transitional	Total
AlgaeBase	1	3	1	3
BOLD	2	2	-	4
Catalogue of Life	5	4	2	7
Catalogue of Fishes	-	1	-	1
Diat.barcode	2	1	1	2
ENA	3	4	2	4
FishBase	1	1	-	2
GBIF	8	6	4	12
NCBI Taxonomy	9	11	4	17
PR2	1	2	1	2
TaxRef	1	1	1	1
UNITE	1	1	1	1
WoRMS	8	16	5	21
Literature	2	5	2	5
Peer expertise	1	-	-	1
Custom Databases	-	1	-	1
No answer	2	1	-	2

3.A.4. Number of species and specimens used for building DNA reference libraries

Highlights:

- A considerable number of replies were not considered in this analysis. Either respondents did not provide data or the information provided was not usable (e.g., non-numerical estimates, comments, etc).
 - No. of analysed cases (no. of species):
 - Marine: 22/25

- Freshwater: 15/20
- Transitional: 6/9
- (no. of specimens):
 - Marine: 18/25
 - Freshwater: 14/20
 - Transitional: 5/9
- Most DNA reference libraries for European aquatic biodiversity included fewer than 200 species (62%), and less than 500 specimens (ca. 29%), with a few reporting within the interval of 1,000 to 3,000 specimens (ca. 19%).

The information regarding the number of species and specimens was missing in a fair number of replies. Coupled with reports providing too general information (such as non-numerical estimates), the pool of answers assessed here were considerably low (Figure 5). For instance, regarding the number of species, analysed freshwater reports included only 75% of the replies (n = 15), while the number of replies that did not provide analysable information or none, were similar between marine and transitional pool of contributions, n = 3, which accounted for 12% and 33.3%, respectively. Further, the number of specimens was even less represented, regardless of the type of environment. For instance, for marine reports, the available information accounted for only 72% of the replies (n = 18; this was the only case where the number of unusable data was greater than no contributions at all); whereas for freshwater and transitional reports, the available data regarding the number of specimens was slightly lower than the information provided on the number of species (freshwater, n = 14, and transitional, n = 5).

The number of species included by each developed(ing) DNA reference libraries that contributed with information in the survey, was found to generally be low; overall fewer than 200 species per reference library, according to the available information. Indeed, around 62% reported to encompass less than 200 species per DNA reference library. Fewer reports were observed the greater the number of species encompassed, particularly for marine taxa, where the number of reports dropped to less than half when moving from fewer than 50 species to the 50-100 species range. Although some variation in the number of species was observed up to 500 species, the general tendency prevailed: the greater the number of species reported to have been included in building DNA reference libraries of European aquatic taxa, fewer replies inferred it. In fact, most of the contributors reported to have generally included fewer than 500 taxa in DNA reference libraries (ca. 72%). Species-richer reports were overall rarely mentioned, with in general one report per environment type. However, two projects stood out from the pool of contributions: one case reported the inclusion of more than ten thousand taxa across all environment types (including groundwater), and another reported to encompass more than fifty thousand taxa; though both were found to targeted Bacteria and Archaea, while the latter exclusively targeted marine-sampled viruses, prokaryotes, and microeukaryotes found in plankton.

Figure 5. Number of species reported to have been targeted for building DNA reference libraries for European aquatic organisms.

Furthermore, the scale for the number of specimens was greater than that observed for the number of species. Indeed, the number of reports using fewer than 50 specimens was considerably low, with only four reports – two from freshwater and two from marine reports (Figure 6). Two clusters were observed in Figure 6, the first that encompass several cases that sequenced less than 500 specimens per DNA reference library, accounting for approximately 29% - mostly represented by marine and freshwater environments; while the second encompassed the use of specimens in the amount between 1000 and 3000 specimens, representing around 19% of the cases. For transitional waters, most reports indicated the use of a number greater than a thousand specimens, however it lacked considerable representation compared to marine and freshwater reported cases.

Figure 6. Numbers of specimens reported to have been included in building DNA reference libraries for European aquatic organisms.

3.A.5. Vouchers

Highlights:

- Most participants (ca. 72%) reported keeping all specimens as vouchers, however several inferred or were presumed to keep at least some of the specimens as vouchers (ca. 18%).
- Bulk of the cases reported to store as voucher whole or partial specimens, and tissue samples (ca. 79%). Permanent slides were used mainly for microscopic organisms, while living and frozen cultures were used for diatoms, and microalgae/ α -cyanobacteria, respectively.
- Voucher specimens are primarily stored in academic or museum (or other public institutions), together accounting for 84% of the cases.
- Ethanol was the most frequently used storage preservative (ca. 46%). Sub-zero temperatures followed with approximately 25% of the cases reporting its employment in voucher material storage.

Preserving specimens as vouchers is a widely adopted practice, irrespective of the environment type. Indeed, around 72% of the contributors reported to have stored all specimens as vouchers, however some further stated to have kept at least some of the specimens as vouchers (ca. 18%). Such was noticed upon further inspection, because the respective respondents indicated to have not kept vouchers at all, but still provided information regarding voucher storage conditions or provided additional details, such as not keeping all of the specimens as vouchers. Hence, approximately 90% of the cases reported to store at least some of the specimens as vouchers. The number of reports inferring to have not kept specimens as vouchers at all was very low, with only two instances found. These two represented cases of projects targeting microscopic organisms, such as Bacteria, Archaea, Virus, and microeukarya; additionally, one of the cases stated to have only included specimens already kept in stored in public institutions, hence voucher storage was not required (this case was marine-specific). Additionally, two cases did indicate whether specimens are stored as voucher.

Figure 7. Number of reports indicating that voucher material was stored for at least some specimens.

Voucher material

Vouchers were reported to consist mostly of whole or partial specimens, or even tissue samples (ca. 79%; Table 9). Permanent slides were also considerably reported, though more exclusively for microscopic and/or single cell organisms such as diatoms and protists. A single case also reported the storage of permanent slides for brown algae. Further, three contributors mentioned using living and frozen cultures as vouchers for certain taxa, of which one of them reported to have used both approaches to store microalgae from all environment types. For instance, living cultures were reported once for diatoms, while frozen cultures were reported twice differently for microalgae and α -Cyanobacteria. Several additional types of voucher materials were mentioned, although these were singular cases. These reports included, e.g., reports such as raw or treated material (such as frustules), both cases respective to diatom storage, and photographic record of the specimen, which was reported from a project targeting freshwater fish (released upon sample collection and photography taken as voucher material). Additionally, two cases did not provide further details on the type of material kept as voucher.

Table 9. List of voucher materials mentioned by those that confirmed to keep voucher material from at least some specimens used to build DNA reference libraries of European aquatic biodiversity.

Voucher material	No. of cases (n = 56)			
	Freshwater	Marine	Transitional	Total
Whole specimen	10	18	3	21
Specimen portion	9	6	2	14
Tissue	3	5	1	9
Permanent slide	3	3	2	4
Living cultures	2	1	1	2
Frozen cultures	1	2	1	2
Other	3	1	1	3
No answer	1	1	1	1

Voucher material storage

Voucher specimens are typically stored in academic or museum collections. However, a more pronounced trend was observed for freshwater biodiversity compared to other environments. There was a strong preference for academic collections, with approximately 49% of the cases reporting to have kept at least some of the specimens as vouchers. These were followed by museums (or other public institutions), representing around 35% of the cases; and to a lesser extent, by private collections (e.g., personal storage), approximately 12%. Other types of institutions were also mentioned, particularly governmental and herbaria.

Ethanol-based storage of voucher material was found to be preferred, according to reported cases (ca. 46%). Sub-zero temperatures followed with just over half of the number of cases reporting ethanol-based storage, accounting for approximately 25%, which encompassed reports of employment of either -20 °C or -80 °C (with a single case using -196 °C) (Table 10). The use of -80 °C did not show any environmental trend; however, -20 °C was roughly preferred for freshwater material. Additionally, formaldehyde was greatly reported for marine material, followed by freshwater material, but none for transitional water. Furthermore, several additional approaches were depicted, although rarely mentioned (each reported once), e.g., canada balsam (for Oligochaetes and leeches from all environment types), propylene ethanol (for freshwater zooplankton), and industrial methylated spirit (IMS; for marine fish). Further approaches included, dried samples, herbarium sheets, living cultures, and permanent slides.

Table 10. Storage conditions reported to be employed in preserving voucher material from specimens used for building DNA reference libraries of European aquatic biodiversity, according to reports inferring the keep voucher material of at least some specimens used.

Storage conditions	No. of cases (n total = 65)			
	Freshwater	Marine	Transitional	Total
-20 °C	7	5	4	9
-80 °C	4	4	3	6
-196 °C	-	1	-	1
Dessicated	3	2	1	4
Ethanol	13	16	7	30
Formaldehyde	3	5	-	7
Other	3	5	3	6
No answer	-	2	-	2

3.A.6. DNA aliquot from reference specimen

Highlights:

- Most respondents reported storing DNA aliquots from DNA extracts, in total approximately 79% of the cases reported.
- DNA aliquots were reported to have been stored, in most of the cases, under sub-temperatures -20 °C and -80 °C were notably the most commonly reported (ca. 59% and 24%, respectively).

The majority of respondents reported storing DNA aliquots from DNA extracts for future studies or assessments (ca. 74%; Figure 8). However, upon further inspection, two cases that initially reported not keeping DNA aliquots were found to keep them to some degree, albeit not systematically. Similarly, several other positive replies indicated that DNA aliquots were not kept for all specimens, hence both

cases were considered positive, so overall around 79% of the cases depicted to keep DNA aliquot for at least sometimes. There were two cases where no information was provided regarding the matter of keeping DNA aliquots. Negative responses regarding the storage of DNA aliquots for future analysis were mainly due to a lack of proper storage conditions or the complete use of the DNA extract volume for genomic sequencing. Additionally, one case reported that DNA extraction and sequencing were conducted from another laboratory, which was the reason DNA was not stored.

Figure 8. Number of reports inferring that DNA aliquots were stored for at least some specimens.

DNA aliquot storage

The storage of DNA aliquots in low-temperature (sub-zero) environments was the preferred approach according to reported cases. Two main temperatures were referenced for preserving DNA aliquots: $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (ca. 59% and 24%, respectively). Desiccation of DNA aliquots was reported only once, and it was further inferred that this was not always the employed approach, with sub-zero storage being the primary method. Additional temperatures were reported, mostly only once each, but a single case further stated to coupled sub-zero temperatures with the use of trehalose to encapsulate and preserve the samples (herein included as other in Table 11).

Table 11. Storage conditions reported to be employed in preserving DNA aliquots from specimens used for building DNA reference libraries of European aquatic biodiversity, according to reports inferring the keep DNA aliquots from at least some specimens used. (*) Several other temperature-based approaches were also reported: $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ coupled with trehalose, $-32\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-70\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and $-8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the latter being a marine-specific reported case.

Storage conditions	No. of cases (n = 37)			
	Freshwater	Marine	Transitional	Total
$-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$	13	12	6	22
$-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$	3	8	3	9
Other $^{\circ}\text{C}$ *	2	1	-	3
Dessicated	1	1	1	1
No answer	1	1	-	2

3.A.7. Molecular markers

Highlights:

- COX1 was the most targeted molecular marker overall, with approximately 30% of the reported cases. Followed by mitochondrial 16S, 18S, and ITS with 15%, 10%, and 7% of the cases, respectively.

A considerable richness of molecular markers was reported to have been sequenced in order to build DNA reference libraries, with 21 specific molecular markers documented (Figure 9). Several other cases further reported to have targeted plastid and mitochondrial genomes, or used microsatellites, however vaguely reported. COX1 was found to be reported by approximately 30% of the cases reported, thus being the most reported molecular marker, according to all contributed input to the survey. Such was followed by mitochondrial 16S, 18S, and ITS, with around 15%, 10%, and 7% of reported cases, respectively, and subsequently followed by 12S, 28S, and histone3 reports (ca. 5%, 4%, and 3%, respectively). The overall trend was found throughout all assessed environments, with the exception of transitional waters, which both COX1 and 16S depicted the same number of mentions, as well as a poorer diversity of molecular markers. Only a single case did not provide information, a freshwater-diatom-specific case.

Figure 9. Proportion of the targeted molecular markers for generating new reference sequences and building DNA reference libraries of European aquatic biodiversity, according to the contributions from the survey. Area sizes are not proportional between different categories.

3.A.8. DNA reference sequences depositing

Highlights:

- Most of the reported cases indicated to have deposited at least some DNA reference sequences in databases, around 82%.

- From those that were inferred to have deposited generated DNA reference sequences, 75% of the cases further informed that such were deposited in public databases. Every non-deposited report further stated that sequences will be deposited in public databases, with an exception in which no information was provided.
- BOLD and NCBI were the most frequently used databases (both ca. 41% each).

Overall, the majority of respondents reported having deposited at least some of the generated DNA reference sequences in a database (ca. 82%; Figure 10), while only five indicated to have not yet deposited any sequences, or at least contributed to a project which such were still not deposited. One of these contributors further reported an additional project for which no information on the state of DNA reference sequences was provided (freshwater-specific). The reasons for not depositing sequences included waiting for publication or still being an active and ongoing project.

DNA reference sequences were reported to have been deposited in public databases in the majority of cases (75%). Non-deposited DNA reference sequences were also expected to be deposited in public databases, except for a single case where no information was provided. Only a single case reported depositing DNA reference sequences in a private/personal database.

Figure 10. Reported cases that indicated to have deposited (or expect to deposit) their DNA reference sequence in a database.

Furthermore, BOLD (Barcode of Life Data System, <https://boldsystems.org/>) and NCBI (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) were the most commonly used databases for depositing DNA reference libraries/sequences (both ca. 41% each), although with environment-specific trends to some degree. In both marine and transitional projects, NCBI submissions were more frequent than BOLD, with 16 and 8 cases reported for NCBI, respectively, compared to 11 and 4 for BOLD (Table 12). In freshwater projects, the opposite was found, with 12 cases reported for BOLD compared to 10 for NCBI. NCBI responses included three categories: “NCBI”, “NCBI-GenBank”, and “NCBI-SRA”, though the former two may be considered as the same category. Several other databases were mentioned, mostly only once, except for the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA, <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/>), which was mentioned twice (Table 12). The NCBI and ENA archives all share data as part of the INSDC.

Table 12. List of databases reported to have been or are expected to be chosen to deposit reference sequences/DNA reference library(ies) of European aquatic biodiversity, according to data pooled from the survey. (*) Encompasses a reply that reported a project that aims to create a public technical repository of verified sequences of French biodiversity.

Database	No. of cases (n total = 51)			
	Freshwater	Marine	Transitional	Total
BOLD	12	11	4	21
Diat.barcode	1	1	1	1
ENA	1	2	1	2
MetaZooGene	-	1	-	1
MIMt	1	1	1	1
NCBI	2	2	1	3
NCBI-GenBank	7	13	6	17
NCBI-SRA	1	1	1	1
Phytool	1	1	1	1
SilvaMod-PR2_CREST	-	1	-	1
VAMPS	1	1	1	1
Future database*	1	1	1	1

3.A.9. Generated metadata

Highlights:

- Around 91% of the assessed cases reported to deposit metadata along with DNA reference sequences generated. Those that have not yet deposited stated that such is indeed expected.
- Metadata standards were not commonly followed, with more than half (ca. 55%) of those that deposited metadata along with DNA reference sequences reporting as so.
- The most commonly generated metadata included project identification, GPS coordinates, person collecting and identifying and depth/altitude.
- Specimens' images were only reported in about half of the replies.

The majority of those contributors that indicated to have deposited the reference sequences in a database, further reported to also deposited respective metadata along (ca. 91%). Among those who had not yet deposited DNA reference sequences in databases, most indicated that they expected to deposit the metadata as well. However, one respondent reported that they do not plan to deposit metadata alongside DNA reference sequences. Additionally, one case, encompassing freshwater, marine, and transitional water environments, provided no information on whether metadata was deposited with DNA reference sequences. This case involved an ongoing project aiming to develop a public technical repository of verified genetic sequences for all biodiversity in France (for further details, see Appendix 6).

While depositing metadata with DNA reference sequences is a common practice, the majority reported not adhering to any metadata standard. Indeed, more than half, approximately 55%, of those cases that deposited metadata were further stated as to not following any metadata standard/format. The unspecified case regarding DNA reference sequences depositing indicated that metadata generated for the sequences did follow a standard, although no specific details were provided. Several

metadata standards/formats were reported to have been followed (see Table 13), with two being highlighted due to their higher frequency of use. These included BOLD metadata requirement - which is not widely considered a standard - and the DNA extension of Darwin Core (hereafter referred to as DNA-Darwin Core).

Table 13. List of metadata standards employed according to questionnaire's submissions that indicated to have deposited DNA reference sequences in a database. "Unknown" values include questionnaire's submissions that did not provide any or acceptable information.

Metadata Standard / Format	No. of cases (n total = 11)			Total
	Freshwater	Marine	Transitional	
BOLD	3	4	2	5
CEN	1	1	1	1
M2B3	-	1	-	1
MGnify/ENA	-	1	-	1
MlxS	1	1	1	1
DarwinCore (DNA extension)	2	4	1	4
NCBI	1	-	1	1
No answer	1	1	1	1

Overall, a pattern was observed for metadata generated for DNA reference library building for European taxa. A group of metadata elements which were most commonly generated, which included: project identification, GPS coordinates of collection, depth/altitude at which the specimen was caught, person responsible for collection and for the identification of the specimen, image/photograph record of the specimen, location at which voucher material is stored along with its identification (usually a code), targeted molecular marker, and the sequenced region (Table 14). On the other hand, the least reported metadata pertained the sample collection date and information regarding accompanying species.

Six different metadata options were proactively added by eight contributors, all of which were barely mentioned. These were grouped together as "other" in Table 14. Overall, these included country information, taxonomic identification, specimen life-stage, and sampling location. Three contributors went further and reported to have used BOLD and MlxS standard metadata, but no specification was given.

Table 14. List of metadata from questionnaire submissions that indicated to have deposited DNA reference sequences in a database. (*) Includes additional answers submitted beyond the listed metadata. Unknown values represent survey submissions that did not provide any or acceptable information.

Metadata	No. of cases (n total = 31)			Total
	Freshwater	Marine	Transitional	
Project ID	11	15	4	23
Specimen identifier	10	12	5	19
Image record	6	11	3	15
Voucher ID	11	13	5	21
Voucher location	10	11	3	19
Specimen collector	11	12	4	21
Collection date	1	1	-	2
GPS coordinates	13	16	6	26
Depth/Altitude	6	14	3	18
Environment	6	8	3	12
Environmental data	2	6	2	8
Accompanying species	-	1	-	1
Tissue	3	7	1	9
Molecular marker	9	13	4	19
PCR primers	7	8	3	13
Sequencing primers	6	7	3	10
Sequencing platform	6	9	4	12
Sequenced region	9	13	4	19

Metadata	No. of cases (n total = 31)			Total
	Freshwater	Marine	Transitional	
Barcode generator	5	6	3	9
Trace files	6	8	1	13
Other*	4	6	3	7
No answer	2	3	2	3

3.A.10. DNA reference library management

Highlights:

- Majority of the deposited DNA reference data was stated to have already been published, approximately 90%, of which 89% further indicated that the data was open-access.
- Most of the reported cases, around 85%, indicated to be following a procedure for accepting or rejecting sequences, while four cases did not provide any information. Several approaches were reported, but sequence length and sequence quality analysis were found to be strongly the most employed according to the survey data
- The employment of taxonomic curation procedures in the management of DNA reference sequences showed lower coverage, with approximately 64% of the cases reporting it. Three cases did not provide information.

Published data and data accessibility

Overall, the majority of the cases stated that DNA reference sequences deposited were also already published (ca. 90%; Figure 11). Unpublished, but already deposited data represented both marine and freshwater cases. Finally the majority of the published data was referred to as open-access (ca. 89%).

Figure 11. Number of reports stating that the generated DNA reference library(ies) have been already published, according to the target environment.

Sequence acceptance procedure

Most of the reported cases, around 85%, indicated to be following a procedure for accepting or rejecting sequences, while four cases did not provide any information. However, it was determined that relevant variation was visible between targeted environment types. Indeed, several approaches were reported for accepting or rejecting genomic sequences in DNA reference libraries, but several were particularly apparent. Sequence length and phylogenetic congruence were reported more frequently in projects targeting marine and transitional biodiversity. Additionally, a single case indicated the use of a sequence filtering procedure, but did not provide details on the methodology.

Table 15. List of reported procedures employed for accepting or rejecting DNA sequences, while filtering generated sequences in building DNA reference libraries of European aquatic biodiversity. (*) Includes procedures ambiguously reported.

Sequence Acceptance Procedure	No. of cases (n total = 33)			
	Freshwater	Marine	Transitional	Total
Voucher vs Barcode identification	1	2	1	2
Laboratory reputation	1	1	1	1
Metadata traceability	6	6	4	9
Metadata quality	1	-	-	1
Expert curation	1	-	-	1
Sequence length	8	13	4	18
Sequence quality	13	18	6	27
Phylogenetic congruence	1	4	1	4
Work in progress	1	1	1	1
Other*	3	4	1	7
No answer	1	-	1	1

Taxonomic curation procedure

The employment of taxonomic curation procedures in the management of DNA reference sequences showed lower coverage, with approximately 64% of the cases reporting it. Three cases did not provide information. Several approaches were mentioned for taxonomy curation in building DNA reference libraries of European biodiversity, with some approaches being more frequently reported or specific to certain environments. Phylogenetic congruence analysis, taxonomic cross-referencing, and consultation with peers/experts represented the majority of the approaches reported (Table 16). Additionally, a considerable number of contributors did not specify which methodology was used for taxonomic curation (n = 4).

Table 16. List of methodologies reported to have been or being employed by DNA reference library(ies) building projects of European aquatic biodiversity for taxonomy curation. (*) Includes procedures ambiguously reported.

Taxonomic Curation Procedure	No. of cases (n total = 25)			
	Freshwater	Marine	Transitional	Total
Phylogenetic congruence	4	5	1	8
Peer/Expert consultation	2	-	1	2
Voucher vs Barcode identification	-	3	-	3
Cross-referencing taxonomy	3	4	3	5
Integrative taxonomic tools	1	-	-	1
BIN discordance check (BOLD)	1	2	1	2
Other*	3	3	1	7
Work in progress	1	1	1	1
No answer	2	3	1	4

Moreover, most reported cases indicated to keep track of the experts responsible for taxonomy curation (84%), with similar coverage across all environment types (Figure 12). However, unavailable

information was found twice (Figure 12). On the other hand, a significant number of reports was also found indicating tracking the different versions of the DNA reference library(ies) post several taxonomic curation events, though to a lesser degree (56%). The number of negative answers was considerably higher than observed for keeping track of curation experts (n = 9, compared to n = 2). Similarly, was also found for “no answer”.

Figure 12. Reported cases that keep track of experts responsible for taxonomy curation of DNA reference library(ies) (left), and that keep track of the several versions of the DNA reference library(ies) generated along taxonomy curation (right). Both barplots are only based cases that reported to employ a taxonomic curation procedure. Bars are colour-coded based on environment type.

3.B. Databases review

A total of 25 public databases were compiled containing DNA reference records of several molecular markers, encompassing a wide range of aquatic taxa. However, only 21 were included in the following analysis. Further details are described in the section 2.B.2.

3.B.1. Databases characterisation

Highlights:

- Most databases are active with ongoing uploads, though few update annually. GreenGenes2 leads with 20 million records, followed by SILVA with 15 million. Some databases are specialised, with FWAlgaeDB for freshwater and others like NISdb and DUFA for marine records, while many do not specify environmental sources.

Most of the assessed databases were found to currently be active (Figure 13), since it was depicted that reference records were still being uploaded into them. Although, majority shown to not be yearly updated (n = 12; Figure 19). Indeed, it was found that no record has been recently uploaded to only five of the databases with no yearly updates (COInr, GSR, EukRibo, Metabarpark, µgreen). Further, although the database’s updates do not have an yearly profile, DNA reference records are still being uploaded into seven databases, namely NISbd, DUFA, SILVA, OTT, MDD, GreenGenes2, and Diat.barcode.

Figure 13. Proportion of the number of databases currently active (left) and depicting yearly updates (right).

Only one of the databases was found to exclusively store DNA sequence data of freshwater organisms (FWAlgaeDB), while four store solely marine records (NISdb, DUFA, Metabarpark, and MZGdb). Still, for two databases such categorisation was not possible since it was not specifically referred to on their websites (PR2 and GTDB). All the remaining do not discriminate the specimen environment-source, hence being approximately 66.7% of the databases (Figure 14).

Figure 14. Type of communities targeted by DNA reference databases analysed. (*) Inconclusive categorisation of PR2 and GTDB targets.

Furthermore, GreenGenes2 was highlighted as the database with the greatest number of records, containing approximately 20 million records. SILVA followed with considerably fewer, but still nearly 15 million records. Subsequently, five other databases followed it with remarkably more than 1 million records stored (UNITE, OTT, MIDORI, COInr, and BOLD Systems). However, the majority of the databases accounted for a hundred thousand records or less (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Number of records or sequences stored on each analysed DNA reference database, according to values found at the time of review of the databases.

3.B.2. Molecular markers

Highlights:

- Most reference databases store data on multiple DNA barcodes or molecular markers. Nearly half store 16S rRNA data, followed by COI and 18S rRNA. About 48% of databases use multiple markers, with BOLD Systems supporting the most markers. μ green and FWAAlgaeDB include unique markers like 23S rRNA and full-length genomes, respectively.

Overall, the reference databases herein analysed stored DNA sequence data of several DNA barcodes or molecular markers. However, not all of them store data from the same molecular marker, but nearly half of them were found to store 16S rRNA data (ca. 47.6%; Table 17), although not all from the same taxa. It was closely followed by COI and 18S rRNA, with approximately 38.1% and 28.6%, respectively. For several other molecular markers, considerable flexibility was found in database storage, namely, 12S rRNA, 28S rRNA, COX2, COX3, ITS2, ND1-4, ND4L, and rbcL.

Multimarker storage in the same database seems very common. Indeed, approximately 47.6% of the databases were found to store data from more than one DNA barcode or molecular marker. BOLD Systems was the database with the most accepted molecular markers and DNA sequence regions accepted ($n = 151$). Other multimarker storing databases included DUFA, Metabarpark, SILVA, UNITE, MIDORI, PR2, Diat.barcode, Phytool, and MZGdb. Beyond BOLD Systems, μ green was found storing data from a molecular marker that was not observed stored in any other analysed database (23S rRNA), while FWAAlgaeDB stores in fact full-length genomes. Data from OTT and MDD were inconclusive.

Table 17. Compiled list of DNA barcode and molecular markers found to be stored by the databases herein analysed, for aquatic biodiversity.

Database	Molecular markers		
COInr	COX1		
NISdb	COX1		
DUFA	COX1	12S rRNA	
GSR	16S rRNA		
EUKRibo	18S rRNA		
MIMt	16S rRNA		
Metabarpark	COX1	18S rRNA	
BOLD Systems	ITS2	D-loop	COX1-LIKE
	rbcL	DYN	CAD
	rbcLa	VDAC	CAD4
	matK	trnL	PGD
	trnH-psbA	rbcL-like	CAD1
	trnL-F	ycf1	TPI
	atpF-atpH	trnK	COX1NMT1
	rpoB	atpB-rbcL	28S-D2-D3
	rpoC1	PSBA	CK1
	COX1	matK-trnK	PER
	COX2	petD-intron	RBM15
	COX3	PY-IGS	TULP
	CytB	rpL32-trnL	28S-D1-D2
ND1	ETS-1	ACE2	
ND2	cp-RPS16-intro	CQ11	
ND3	5-8S	28S-D3-D5	

Database	Molecular markers		
	ND4	12S rRNA	GAPDH
	ND4L	CHD-Z	fbpA
	ND5-0	MB2-EX2-3	IDH
	ND6	MC1R	MDH
	28S rRNA	COX1-NUMT	DDC
	NBC-COX1	H3	ENO
	18S rRNA	IRBP	ArgK
	5S-23S	DBY-EX7-8	RpS2
	atp6	RAG2	RpS5
	matR	R35-intron	DDX23
	matK-like	NGFB	WSP
	psbK-psbl	R35	RPL37
	16S rRNA	Rho	EF1-alpha-5P
	PsbA-like	PKD1	CsIV
	COX1-PSEUDO	TMO-4C4	HflV
	MutS-like	PLAGL2	COX1NMT2
	16S rRNA-ND2	RAG1	CYTB-NUMT
	COX2-COX1	S7	H3-NUMT
	ND4L-MSH	atp6-atp8	LWRHO
	ND6-ND3	RNF213	CHOLC
	ADR	ENC1	H4
	TYR	MYH6	28S-D7
	28S-D3	EF1-alpha	28S-D9-D10
	Wnt1	RPB2	ATP1A
	28S-D2	ApsaB	EPRS
	CADH	COX2-COX2I	TS
	coxA	RBCL-5P	ATP8
	ftsZ	psbA-3P	RpS4-trnS
	sca4	RPB1	nucLSU
	ntcA	Beta-tubulin	UPA
	PSA	AOX-fmt	Msp4
	psbC	mtSSU	hcpA
	e-gene	trnD-trnY-trnEA	
	tufA	FL-COX1	
	EF2	CAD-5P	
SILVA	16S rRNA	18S rRNA	28S rRNA
UNITE	ITS1 ITS2	ITS3 ITS4	
MIDORI	COX1 COX2 COX3 12S rRNA 16S rRNA	A6 A8 CytB ND1 ND2	ND3 ND4 ND4L ND5 ND6
PR2	16S rRNA	18S rRNA	
OTT	NA		
MDD	NA		
GreenGenes2	16S rRNA		
µgreen	23S rRNA		
Diat.barcode	COX1 18S rRNA	ITS2 rbcL	

Database	Molecular markers		
Phytool	16S rRNA 18S rRNA	23S rRNA rbcL	
GTDB	16S rRNA		
MZGdb	COX1 16S rRNA	18S rRNA 12S rRNA	28S rRNA
FWAlgaeDB	Genome		

3.B.3. Metadata

Highlights:

- Mandatory metadata was only available for BOLD Systems and MDD, including taxonomic assignments and sample locations. While GPS coordinates were present in about a third of databases (e.g., BOLD Systems, SILVA, UNITE), most databases lacked detailed workflow information such as sample collection and sequence protocols. Only NISdb, DUFA, and MDD provided comprehensive workflow details.

Mandatory metadata information was only present in two databases, namely BOLD Systems and MDD; which generally encompassed taxonomic assignment of the DNA sequence record, ID (e.g., sample, record, storage record, etc), sample location (e.g., biome, continent, country), although further includes environmental features. See Table 18 for further details. Nevertheless, although not considered as mandatory, according to the available information, GPS coordinates data has also been widely represented for several DNA reference records. However, merely a third of the databases were found to provide such information, which included the following databases: BOLD Systems, SILVA, UNITE, PR2, MDD, Diat.barcode, and MZGdb.

Table 18. List of mandatory metadata requested while uploading barcode sequences onto a DNA reference database

Database	Mandatory metadata	
BOLD Systems	Sample ID	Institution storing
	Field ID	Taxonomic ranks
	Museum ID	Country/Ocean
MDD	Phylum	Country
	Organism	Sample
	UNITE ID	Biosample
	ZOTU	Biome
	Continent	Environmental feature

Furthermore, most of the databases do not allow the uploading of information regarding steps taken in the study's workflow, such as, sample collection, DNA extraction, sequence protocol (URL to protocol.io), sequencing strategy, and sequence analysis (Figure 16). In fact, COInr allows merely the upload of the former and latter, while Diat.barcode does not allow information regarding the latter two. Additionally, only three of the databases were found to enable all of the mentioned workflow steps (NISdb, DUFA, and MDD), whereas EukRibo was found to not allow information solely of DNA extraction.

Figure 16. Proportion of the DNA reference databases that enable for information from study's pipeline, encompassing methodology employed for sample collection and DNA extraction, whether sequence protocol link is provided (e.g., URL to protocol.io), the general sequencing strategy opted, as well as sequence analysis workflow, to be uploaded.

3.B.4. Taxonomic identification and curation

Highlights:

- Taxonomic curation is used by about 86% of DNA reference databases, except Metabarpark, OTT, and GreenGenes2. Most databases (76%) lack confidence levels for taxonomic identifications, with only a few—EukRibo, BOLD Systems, UNITE, MDD, and GreenGenes2—offering this feature. GSR lacks taxonomic identification features but includes taxon names.

Taxonomic curation appears to be a common procedure occurring in DNA reference databases analysed (Figure 17). Indeed, 85.7% of the databases were found to have a curation system, the only exceptions found being Metabarpark, OTT, and GreeGenes2. Additionally, curation of the taxonomic identifications of DNA sequence data is crucial for reliable data, however, most of the databases do not have a feature which provides a level of confidence between the DNA record and its taxonomic identification (ca. 76.2%; Figure 17). EukRibo, BOLD Systems, UNITE, MDD, and GreenGenes2 were found to be the only ones here analysed featuring such features.

Figure 17. Proportion of DNA reference databases that feature a taxonomic curation of the reference records (left), and that provide a system measuring confidence level of the curation provided. (*) Inconclusive data on μ green's taxonomic curation.

Furthermore, GSR was the sole database herein analysed that does not provide a feature for taxonomic identification of DNA sequences. But all of them have taxa names of the identification represented for each record.

3.B.5. Database accessibility

Highlights:

- Most databases (81%) have a standardised structure, but MIDORI, OTT, μ green, and MZGdb lack web interfaces. About 71% do not offer API support, and 62% lack desktop or console support. PR2, OTT, MDD, and Phytool provide all access types, while GreenGenes2 and MIDORI offer single-access methods. BOLD Systems and UNITE support web interfaces with APIs, and SILVA, GTDB, and FWAAlgaeDB offer both web and desktop access.

Overall, the majority of the databases showed a considerably consistent structure, approximately 81%. Only four of them were found to have no standardised structure, namely MIDORI, OTT, μ green, and MZGdb. In fact, the latter two do not have an web interactive interface enabling browsing available data, and performing upload or download of data. However, such was found for more than half of the databases analysed, but, except μ green and MZGdb, all of them still depicted to be structurally consistent. Furthermore, there is no API (Application Programming Interface) support, as well as, desktop or console support, for the majority of the database assessed (approximately 71% and 62%, respectively; Figure 18). In fact, almost half of the records ($n = 10$) were shown to neither have an web interface, API support, desktop nor console support (COInr, NISbd, DUFA, GSR, EukRibo, MIMt, Metabarpark, μ green, Diat.barcode, and MZGdb). PR2, OTT, MDD, and Phytool were the only herein databases that supported all of them. On the other hand, GreenGenes2 and MIDORI were found to be the sole single access approach database, respectively supporting desktop and console access and having a web interface that allows to browse and download data. Finally, three other databases are depicted to have support for both (SILVA, GTDB, and FWAAlgaeDB), whereas the remaining have a web interface while also providing an API (BOLD Systems and UNITE).

Figure 18. Proportion of the DNA reference databases that have an interactive web interface providing a somewhat user-friendly of browsing and accessing reference barcodes, or display either API or desktop/console support.

3.B.6. Upload and download of data and metadata

Highlights:

- DNA sequence data can be exported in 12 file formats, with FASTA being the most common (71.4%). Most databases offer only one export format, with MZGdb providing the most flexibility (FASTA, MOTHUR, CSV, PSV). Metadata can be exported in 13 formats, with CSV and FASTA being the most common.
- Most databases allow separate downloads of data and metadata, often linked by a common ID, but 81% do not provide direct links to external metadata.
- For uploads, FASTA is the most common format for DNA sequences, and TEXT files are frequently used for metadata. μ green supports the most formats, while BOLD Systems also offers diverse metadata upload options.

DNA sequence data can be exported in many different file formats. Indeed, a total of 12 formats were found (Figure 19). A considerable number of databases showed more options of data export, with multiple file formats available, however the majority provided the option of only exporting it in a single file format ($n = 11$). In fact, within the latter group, the majority allowed download of it in FASTA (ca. 54.5%), while the remaining allowed export of DNA sequence data as either CSV, TEXT, or TRACE. Following, two file format options appeared to follow single-file format export, which then was followed by three, and four, respectively. MZGdb was the database with greater flexibility in exporting DNA sequence data, being the only one with four available options (FASTA, MOTHUR, CSV, and PSV). FASTA was found to be the most common option of exporting DNA sequence data from reference databases, available in approximately 71.4%. Although all of the file formats provide different approaches in reading data with several DNA sequences, TAX files merely export taxonomic data of each sequence in plain text (provided by μ green).

Additionally, a similar number of file formats was found for exporting metadata associated with DNA sequence data, but the number of unknown file formats was greater. Exportable metadata appears to be available in 13 formats (Figure 19). Similarly, the majority of the databases allow exporting metadata in a single file format ($n = 9$), while CSV yielded more providing databases (33.3%), followed by FASTA, TEXT, XLSX, and YAML. BOLD Systems, Open Tree Life Taxonomy, and UNITE appear to provide the greatest diversity of metadata exportable file formats - three each. FWAlgaeDB, was the only one found that does not feature a metadata exporting system. Overall, the most available format was also FASTA ($n = 4$), closely followed by CSV and TEXT formats (each $n = 3$).

Several approaches have been followed in terms of how sequence data and metadata are linked upon download. However, the majority of the databases provide a way to download two different files, although somehow always linked. For instance, COInr, GSR, and EukRibo allow the user to download both separate files as CSV, but both have included a common column with a form of ID (e.g., the former identifies it with Tax ID). Similarly, can be found for MIMt and Metabarpark, though in a different file format. Additionally, BOLD Systems, Phytool, MIDORI, and PR2, provides the option of either downloading data and metadata separately or merged in a single file, but for the latter two, such depends on the type of output. On the other hand, both SILVA and UNITE allow download of data and metadata merged as an archived file (GZIP file from SILVA). For further details how each database links its sequence data and respective metadata, see Table 19.

Furthermore, where metadata may not be stored in the same database as DNA reference sequences are stored, it is then imperative to provide a link or path to where it can be accessed. However, the majority of those do not provide it (ca. 81%). OTT, MDD, Phytool, and FWAlgaeDB were found to be the only DNA reference databases to provide a URL, or URI, or another type of link that indicates where metadata is stored.

The number of unknowns regarding file formats accepted by each database for upload DNA sequence data was remarkably high, being only available information of μ green, PR2, MZGdb, MDD, GTDB, FWAlgaeDB, and BOLD Systems (33.3% of the analysed databases; similarly found for metadata) (Figure 20). The former was found to be the most flexible, accepting three types of data files (BIOCOM-PIPE, MOTHUR, and TAX - however the latter merely includes taxonomic information); followed by PR2

and GTDB, that allow upload of TEXT files, but uniquely FASTA, and separate files available, respectively. FASTA files appear to be the most common way of uploading DNA sequence data to reference databases (n = 5). Similarly, metadata wise, µgreen depicted the greatest file format acceptability (Figure 20), however followed by BOLD Systems, which allow upload of metadata via XLS or XLSX files. TEXT files were found to be the most common approach to upload metadata associated with DNA sequence data.

Figure 19. Files format of data/sequences and metadata when exporting it from DNA reference databases analysed.

Table 19. Description of how each database linked DNA sequence data and its respective metadata upon downloading it.

Database	Data and Metadata link (after download)
COLnr GSR EukRibo	Two CSV files, sharing some sort of ID column
NISdb	Merged in the same CSV file
BOLD Systems Phytool	Either merged or separate
MIDORI PR2	Either merged or separate, depending on the type of output
MIMt Metabarpark	Two separate files, with shared ID column

Database	Data and Metadata link (after download)
SILVA UNITE	Merged in a archive file (the former in GZIP format)
DUFA	File has to be compiled with a script
GreenGenes2	No metadata
OTT	Data is linked to OneZoom, which allows for searching the data in NCBI. It is also linked to Encyclopedia of Life, but currently it is not working
MDD	Data linked to UNITE community
µgreen	Data in BIOCOM_PIPE, Mothur or Taxonomy only format
Diat.barcode	Database is a large excel file (merged)
GTDB MZGdb FWAlgaeDB	None

Figure 20. Files format of data/sequences and metadata when uploading it from DNA reference databases analysed.

3.C. Large Language Model (LLM)

Highlights:

- From the 1607 papers compiled, LLM processed only 1440.
- From the latter, the LLM processed 60% (n = 867) in search of molecular markers. ITS, COX1, 16S (no discrimination between prokaryotic and mitochondrial), and 18S, were the most reported, in this order.
- Nineteen molecular markers were found to be barely reported.
- For searching the DNA reference databases reported, the LLM processed 62% (n = 898) of the 1440 papers. A total of 55 databases were found, of which only 20% were relevant (more than 10 reports). NCBI GenBank and SILVA were highlighted, both with ca. 38% of the reports, being followed by BOLD, UNITE, EMBL, RDP, PR2, and GreenGenes, which all together accounted for 42%.

The LLM was used to automatically analyse text of the biological papers found on the Internet. In this deliverable it was used to extract markers and reference databases used in the described experiments. From a pool of 1607 papers downloaded with crawler, the LLM was able to process 1440 papers. The dataset contains the DOI number of downloaded publications, title, full content of the paper, content of the paragraphs (not for all papers), information if the paper is on eDNA data and the responses for the questions that LLM responded. All attributes are text data apart from eDNA info which is logical value. Full database with the results from LLM is accessible in <link to database dump>.

3.C.1. Molecular markers

For molecular markers data, the LLM was able to extract information from around 60% of the processed papers (n = 867), however, less than 2% of the reports did not represent any molecular marker (e.g., primers). This process allowed to extract every molecular markers' designation, pooling a list of 35 unique molecular markers cited to have been used for building DNA reference libraries for DNA European taxa (Figure 21). Four molecular markers were reported in approximately 66% of the processed papers, namely COX1, 16S, ITS, and 18S, in the respective order (each representing approximately 19%, 17%, 15%, and 14%, respectively). However, no detailed information was available representing the proportion of prokaryotic and mitochondrial 16S rRNA reported. Other molecular markers such as 12S, rbcL, trnL, and 28S were also considerably reported (ranging 7-12 reports). Several other molecular markers/regions (n = 19) were found to have been reported from the pool of 854 processed papers, however all of them were reported less than ten times.

3.C.2. Reference databases

Furthermore, the LLM was able to find DNA reference databases from approximately 62% of the processed papers (n = 898). Overall, the model identified a total of 55 DNA reference databases, of which, only a fifth was reported more than ten times (n = 11; Figure 21). All the remaining were considered as "other". NCBI GenBank and SILVA were highlighted by representing around 38% alone. These were followed by BOLD, UNITE, EMBL, RDP, PR2, and GreenGenes, which each depicted half, or less than half, of the two previously mentioned (all together represented ca. 43%). Further, several reports were found stating to have opted to use custom databases (ca. 4%).

Figure 21. Databases pooled from 898 papers processed using the LLM, and the number of papers reporting them. “Other” include all databases than accounted for less than 10 reports each (n = 44).

4. Discussion and Conclusions

4.A. Scope of survey's results

- Moderate number of accepted replies from the questionnaire, but with a reasonable geographic scope.
- Regional scale projects were the most represented, predominantly covering marine and freshwater taxa, and a few pertaining groundwater and terrestrial organisms.
- Replies covered the full spectrum of organisms from prokaryotes to protists, fungi, plants and animals, but were largely dominated by Metazoa, most pertaining to invertebrates and, in some cases, also fish.

4.B Specimen source, taxonomic identification and processing

- Specimens for the reference libraries were predominantly collected from the natural environment, followed by public collections including culture collections.
- Private collections (i.e. non-publicly available) constitute a minor, but still sizable source of specimens).
- Prevalence of specimens collected from the wild may be a consequence of many aquatic animals being preserved in formalin or 70% ethanol in museum and other collections, making them inadequate for DNA isolation and barcoding.
- Metazoa were by far the most represented taxa in reference libraries. Among these crustaceans, insects, and fish were the most common. This was expected, as fish and invertebrates are key biomonitoring components in EU directives (e.g. WFD), but some invertebrate groups appear to be still poorly represented.
- Morphology-based taxonomic identification of specimens was the most used approach, as expected for metazoan-dominated libraries.
- Notably, about a quarter of replies reports using both molecular and morphological approaches, and a small percentage point solely to molecular approach, the latter being mostly associated with microbial libraries.
- The great majority of morphological identifications were made by level I and II experts, thereby a high level of accuracy is anticipated for those records.
- Regarding the rank of identification, most specimens were identified to species, but a sizable number of replies indicated also genus-level and family-level assignments. The latter are probably more prevalent in microbial collections in which an important portion of the records are identified above species-level.
- Sources of cross-reference source for taxonomy were diverse and dependent on the environment or taxa used. For example, WoRMS was the main choice for marine and transition waters, whereas for freshwaters it was WoRMS along with NCBI and GBIF that dominated. Despite the variety of sources, it should be noted that several of the reported cross-referenced databases were inter-linked (e.g. FishBase and WoRMS), so that these libraries may be using the same reference taxonomy although cross-referenced to different databases/sources.

- There were few replies with quantitative data on the number of specimens and species included in the reference libraries. The available replies indicate that most libraries have less than 200 species and below 500 specimens.
- A detailed gap-analysis of the taxonomic and species coverage (i.e., precise taxa and species missing from the reference libraries), is beyond the scope of this report. However, there are several comprehensive gap-analyses published (e.g. Weigand et al., 2019, Leite al., 2022, Csabai et al., 2023, Lavrador et al., 2023), that indicate considerable variation among taxonomic groups in the degree of completeness. Overall, libraries for freshwater organisms appear to be more complete than for those inhabiting marine and transitional waters, which have low representation of some dominant and diverse groups (e.g. gastropods). Globally, fish species are much better represented than invertebrates (Weigand et al., 2019). On the other hand, there are still many gaps in non-indigenous marine invertebrate species, which due to their potential environmental impact deserve particular attention in marine biomonitoring programs (Lavrador et al., 2023). Finally, it must be stressed that the gap evaluation for microbial organisms is far more complex than for macro-organisms.
- Most participants (74%) reported keeping vouchers, primarily whole or parts of specimens, and tissue samples. Specimens are primarily stored in academic or museum collections. For the verification purposes, specimens may be kept for relatively long periods in the laboratories until completion of the reference library or publication, and only posteriorly deposited in a museum or other institutional collections. In case of microbial organisms (e.g., microalgae, fungi, protists) specimens can be kept alive in institutional culture collections.
- Ethanol was the most frequently used storage preservative, especially for freshwater and marine specimens, followed by sub-zero temperatures. However, most replies did not mention the ethanol concentration, which may have a strong impact in the ability to recover DNA in the future.
- In most cases, aliquots from DNA extracts are stored, with preference for low-temperature storage, between -20 °C to -80 °C. Long-term sustainable management of stored DNA extracts may be demanding for smaller laboratories without LIMS or permanent staff, but it is not possible to know from the questionnaire if all cases reported have such capabilities.

4.C. DNA sequence data, metadata and data management

- There is a broad diversity of molecular markers used in reference libraries of aquatic organisms, with notably higher diversity reported for marine organisms' libraries.
- As expected, globally and partially for each environment, COX1 was the most represented marker, presumably the majority of it consisting of sequence data from the formal animal barcode region at the 5' end of the gene (Hebert et al., 2003).
- The second most represented marker is the mitochondrial 16S rRNA, particularly prevalent in transitional and freshwater environments. For this one, and other markers lacking a standard barcode region, such as 12S rRNA (often used for fish and other vertebrates monitoring), it is not possible to know whether the sequences correspond to the same region within the gene, unless they consist of the full gene sequence, which is seldom the case. Indeed, a large number of the publicly available sequences for 12S is composed of a mosaic of segments from different regions within the gene, often restricted to the few base pairs delimited by the most commonly used metabarcoding primers (e.g. see Fontes et al., in press). This makes it hard to appreciate the taxonomic coverage and effectiveness of the reference library for general DNA-based monitoring. For the markers lacking a standard region, reference libraries should be composed

of full-gene reference sequences, or, alternatively, a standard region that covers a large-enough section of the gene should be proposed.

- Among the replies that reported to have published DNA sequence data, most also reported depositing the associated metadata, but with varying degree of completeness. Metadata standards were followed in about half of the cases, the majority of which referred to BOLD and Darwin core.
- The most frequently deposited metadata included: project identification, GPS coordinates, voucher ID and location, person collecting and identifying specimens, depth/altitude. Collection date was mentioned only in two cases; a surprisingly low number for a metadata element which is highly relevant for specimens collected from the wild.
- Among the sequence-associated metadata, the molecular marker and sequenced region were also frequently recorded, but other elements such as PCR and sequencing primers, trace files and sequencing platforms were provided in less than half of the cases. These are extremely relevant metadata elements, notably the trace files that are required for BOLD records that are standard-compliant (Ratnasingham et al. 2024).
- Images are of high relevance for verification and validation of records, but only about half of the cases reported depositing images. Acquiring images can be a demanding task, particularly in small laboratories that lack equipment or personnel for high-throughput production of good quality images.
- Overall, resulting survey's metadata deposition, it is patent that many of the "obligatory" metadata elements proposed for aquatic life by Rimet et al. (2021) are missing from the reference libraries, particularly when considering the "recommended" or taxon-specific metadata elements. These findings will be examined in the scope of WP3 and considered for eDNAqua-plan data standards recommendations.
- Most libraries included in the survey have been published and are open-access. The sequence acceptance procedure is primarily based on sequence quality, then sequence length, and also metadata traceability, but the latter in less than one third of the cases. Compared to the comprehensive sequence acceptance procedures described in Pentinsaari et al. (2020) for COX1 barcodes, these few criteria appear very limited. However, this may be a result of the structure of the survey's form, which did not allow for detailed replies. Nevertheless, it is advisable to set up general and largely recognised minimal criteria for sequence acceptance in reference libraries, and the data here collected will inform WP3 recommendations on this point.
- Taxonomic curation procedures are applied in just under 65% of the libraries. The curation procedures vary considerably and are not necessarily equivalent. Phylogenetic congruence checks were only reported for about one third of the libraries with curation procedures. Taxonomic curation is essential for reference libraries accuracy and usefulness. Ambiguities and discordances between species names and molecular data have been extensively recorded (e.g. Radulovici et al, 2021), but reference libraries with complete and sound taxonomic curation procedures are still rare (e.g. R-Syst::diatom, Rimet et al., 2016). A general appraisal and recommendations for reference libraries auditing annotation and curation systems will be carried out in the scope of WP3.

4.D. LLM

- From over 850 papers processed by the LLM, the most reported markers, ordered by prevalence, were COX1, 16S (no discrimination between prokaryotic and mitochondrial), ITS, and 18S. Other sixteen molecular markers were barely reported. A total of 55 reference databases were found, of which only 20% were relevant (more than 10 reports). NCBI GenBank

and SILVA were highlighted, both with ca. 38% of the reports, being followed by BOLD, UNITE, EMBL, RDP, PR2, and GreenGenes, which altogether accounted for 42%.

4.E. Databases review

- Most of the repositories were updated periodically, but only 5 annually. Twenty repositories covered all aquatic environments, while only four focus on marine waters and one contains only records for freshwaters.
- Half of the repositories store data on multiple molecular markers, with 16S rRNA data being the most abundant, followed by COX1 and 18S rRNA.
- Most repositories lack detailed workflow information such as sample collection and sequence protocols. Some taxonomic curation is used by nearly all repositories but, at the same time, most lack confidence levels for taxonomic identifications.
- Most repositories have a standardised structure, but they usually do not offer API, desktop or console support. Four repositories lack web interfaces. FASTA is the most common format in which the data can be downloaded from the databases.

4.F. Final conclusions

- This study underlines the multitude of reference libraries existing in Europe. Some reference libraries are very large and hosting various organisms, with a professional IT infrastructure but relatively poorly curated. On the contrary, other libraries are well curated by experts in taxonomy of specific groups of organisms, gathering many metadata associated to the barcode, but of smaller size and with a relatively poor IT infrastructure.
- Overall, the status of reference barcode libraries for European aquatic organisms is suboptimal. Definitely, the libraries are not homogeneous in terms of comprehensiveness, metadata quality, auditability, taxonomic curation, accessibility and interoperability. The reason for this heterogeneity may relate to the fact that the libraries have various objectives and are used in different ways. Unfortunately, the different uses of these libraries have not been taken into account in the framework of this study. However, we would recommend that the choice of the necessary metadata to keep in a reference library, which has to be decided in WP3.1, must enable the managers (e.g. taxonomic curators) and the end users of the reference libraries to have confidence in it.
- DNA reference libraries with incomplete metadata may still be useful, but their records may not be auditable / verifiable.
- Strong investment is needed to further complete, improve and manage aquatic European barcode reference libraries.
- In the meantime, auditing and curation systems are needed to screen the available libraries, annotate the quality of the records, and select those that should be used in aquatic monitoring.

5. References

- Csabai Z, Čiamporová-Zaťovičová Z, Boda P, Čiampor Jr F (2023) 50%, not great, not terrible: Pan-European gap-analysis shows the real status of the DNA barcode reference libraries in two aquatic invertebrate groups and points the way ahead. *Science of The Total Environment*, volume 863, 160922. ISSN 0048-9697. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.160922>
- Fontes J, Kato K, Pires R, Soares P, Costa FO (2024) Benchmarking the discrimination power of commonly used markers and amplicons in marine fish (e)DNA (meta)barcoding. *ARPHA Preprints*, 5, e128777. <https://doi.org/10.3897/arphapreprints.e128777>
- Hebert PDN, Cywinska A, Ball SL, deWaard R (2013) Biological identifications through DNA barcodes. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series B: Biological Sciences*, 270(1512), pp. 313-321. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2002.2218>
- Kahle D, Wickham H (2013) ggmap: Spatial Visualization with ggplot2. *The R Journal*, 5(1), pp. 144-161.
- Lavrador AS, Fontes JT, Vieira PE, Costa FO, Duarte S (2023) Compilation, Revision, and Annotation of DNA Barcodes of Marine Invertebrate Non-Indigenous Species (NIS) Occurring in European Coastal Regions. *Diversity* 2023, 15, 174. <https://doi.org/10.3390/d15020174>
- Leite BR, Vieira PE, Teixeira MAL, Lobo-Arteaga J, Hollatz C, Borges LMS, Duarte S, Troncoso JS, Costa FO (2020) Gap-analysis and annotated reference library for supporting macroinvertebrate metabarcoding in Atlantic Iberia. *Regional Studies in Marine Science*, 36, 101307.
- Pentinsaari M, Ratnasingham S, Miller SE, Hebert PDN (2020) BOLD and GenBank revisited – Do identification errors arise in the lab or in the sequence libraries? *PLoS One* 15(4): e0231814. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0231814>
- Posit Team (2024): RStudio: Integrated Development Environment for R. Posit Software , PBC, Boston, MA. <http://www.posit.co/>
- R Core Team (2024). R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. <https://www.R-project.org/>
- Radulovici AE, Vieira PE, Duarte S, Teixeira MAL, Borges LMS, Deagle B, Majaneva S, Redmond N, Schultz JA, Costa FO (2021) Revision and annotation of DNA barcode records for marine invertebrates: report of the 8th iBOL conference hackathon. *Metabarcoding and Metagenomics* 5: 207–217. <https://doi.org/10.3897/mbmg.5.67862>
- Ratnasingham S, Wei C, Chan D, Agda J, Agda J, Ballesteros-Mejia L, Ait Boutou H, El Bastami Z M, Ma E, Manjunath R, Rea D, Ho C, Telfer A, McKeowan J, Rahulan M, Steinke C, Dorsheimer J, Milton M, Hebert PDN (2024) "BOLD v4: A Centralized Bioinformatics Platform for DNA-Based Biodiversity Data." In *DNA Barcoding: Methods and Protocols*, pp. 403-441. Chapter 26. New York, NY: Springer US.
- Rimet F, Aylagas E, Borja A, Bouchez A, Canino A, Chauvin C, Chonova T, Ciampor Jr F, Costa FO, Ferrari BJD, Gastineau R, Goulon C, Gugger M, Holzmann M, Jahn R, Kahlert M, Kusber W-H, Laplace-Treytoure C, Leese F, Leliaert F, Mann DG, Marchand F, Méléder V, Pawlowski J, Rasconi S, Rivera S, Rougerie R, Schweizer M, Trobajo R, Vasselon V, Vivien R, Weigand A, Witkowski A, Zimmermann J, Ekrem T (2021) Metadata standards and practical guidelines for specimen and DNA curation when building barcode reference libraries for aquatic life. *Metabarcoding and Metagenomics* 5: 17-33. <https://doi.org/10.3897/mbmg.5.58056>

- Rimet F, Chaumeil P, Keck F, Kermarrec L, Vasselon V, Kahlert M, Franc A, Bouchez A (2016) R-Syst::diatom: an open-access and curated barcode database for diatoms and freshwater monitoring. Database, <https://doi.org/10.1093/database/baw016>
- Tennekes M (2023) treemap: Treemap Visualization. R package version 2.4.4.
- Touvron H, Martin L, Stone K, Alber P, Almahairi A, Babaei Y, Bashlykov N, Batra S, Bhargava P, Bhosale S, Bikel D, Blecher L, Ferrer C, Chen M, Cucurull G, Esiobu D, Fernandes J, Fu J, Fu W, Fuller B, Inan H, Kardas M, Kerkez V, Khabsa M, Kloumann I, Korenev A, Koura PS, Lachaux MA, Avriil T, Lee J, Liskovich D, Lu Y, Mao Y, Martinet X, Mihaylov T, Mishra P, Molybog I, Nie Y, Poulton A, Reizenstein J, Rungta R, Saladi K, Schelten A, Silva R, Smith EM, Subramanian R, Tan XE, Tang B, Fan A, Kamadur M, Narang S, Rodriguez A, Stojnic R, Edunov S, Scialom T (2023) Llama 2: Open Foundation and Fine-Tuned Chat Models. arXiv preprint arXiv:2307.09288.
- Ward RD (2012) FISH-BOL, A Case Study for DNA Barcodes. In: Kress W, Erickson D (eds) DNA Barcodes: Methods in Molecular Biology, 858, pp. 423-439. Chapter 21. Humana Press, Totowa, NJ. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-61779-591-6_21
- Weigand H, Beerman AJ, Čiampor F, Costa FO, Csabai Z, Durte S, Geiger MF, Grabowski M, Rimet F, Rulik B, Strand M, Szucsich N, Weigand AM, Willassen E, Wyler SA, Bouchez A, Borja A, Čiamporová-Zaťovičová Z, Ferreira S, Dijkstra KDB, Eisendle U, Freyhof J, Gadawski P, Graf W, Haegerbaeumer A, van der Hoorn BB, Japoshvili B, Keresztes L, Keskin E, Leese F, Macher JN, Mamos T, Paz Guy, Pešić V, Pfannkuchen DM, Pfannkuchen MA, Price BW, Rinkevich B, Teixeira MAL, Várbió G, Ekrem T (2019) DNA barcode reference libraries for the monitoring of aquatic biota in Europe: Gap-analysis and recommendations for future work. Science of the Total Environment 678: 499-524. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.04.247>
- Wickham W (2016) ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis. Springer-Verlag New York.

Contributions

- Michal Grabowski, Spiros Papakostas, Filipe Costa, Peter Woollard and Frédéric Rimet designed the study and contributed to report writing.
- UMinho team (Jorge Moutinho, Pilar Cabezas and Filipe Costa), did the majority of the work with coordinating and collating the questionnaire, preparing reports' graphs and tables, and writing the report's text.
- Ioannis Kavakiotis and Dawid Krawczyk did the majority of the compilation of the bioinformatics inventory for reference libraries databases.
- Peter Woollard, performed the secondary computational analysis of the databases and questionnaire, and critically reviewed and edited the report.
- Dawid Krawczyk and Michal Seweryn performed the LLM and wrote the relevant methodology section.
- Arne Beerman and Florian Leese contributed extensively to critical reviewing and editing of the report.
- Michal Grabowski and Spiros Papakostas co-led the WP2 and provided much guidance and motivation to all.
- Most people on the WP2 and WP3 teams provided input into the metadata properties needed to be collected.
- We are thankful to all researchers that replied to our survey and contributed with data from their projects to this report.

Appendix (Supplementary Material)

Appendix 1. Questionnaire structure

The questionnaire was structured in three main components: i) the first encompass point in order to get relevant information identifying whomever replied to it, ii) the second encompassed the bulk of the questions targeting barcode production, and iii) the latter encompassed questions more specific to DNA reference library management. This survey was adapted into two formats - Google Forms and Spreadsheet format - which followed the following general structure:

Survey section I - Affiliation

Q. What institution are you affiliated with?

[Open answer]

Q. Which type of institution are you affiliated with?

- Academic institution
- Governmental institution
- Non-Governmental institution
- [Open answer]

Q. In which country is the institution you are affiliated with located?

[Open answer]

Survey section II - Barcode Production

Q1. Please, list the project(s) you contributed/developed in building DNA reference libraries.

[Open answer]

Q2. What was the scale of the project?

- Local
- Regional (national)
- Regional (international)
- National
- International
- [Open answer]

Q3. Which type of aquatic environment have you created reference sequences for?

- Marine (coastal, continental shelf, abyssal, etc)
- Freshwater (river, lake, wetland, etc)
- Transitional
- Groundwater
- [Open answer]

Q4. What was the origin of the sequenced specimens?

- Collected in nature
- Cultures
- Museum and other public collections
- Personal/Local collections
- [Open answer]

Q5. In the case of cultures/collections originating reference specimens, from which institution are they?

[Open answer]

Q6. Have any of the specimens that you sequenced originated from Europe?

- Yes
- No

Q7. If yes, could you specify the region/locality where reference specimens were collected?

[Open answer]

Q8. For which taxa have you contributed in building DNA reference libraries? Please, specify to which environment if you mentioned multiple.

[Open answer]

Q9. How were the reference specimens identified?

[Open answer]

Q10. What is the level of expertise of the identifier? Please be specific if you mentioned multiple taxa.

Note: in this point a table with a more detailed description of each level of identification was provided adapted from Ward (2012)

- Level 1 - Highly reliable identification
- Level 2 - Identification made with a high degree of confidence at all levels
- Level 3 - Identification made with high confidence to genus but less to species
- Level 4 - Identification with limited confidence
- Level 5 - Identification superficial
- [Open answer]

Q11. At what taxonomic level are the specimens you have sequenced usually identified?

- Phylum
- Class
- Order
- Family
- Genus
- Species
- [Open answer]

Q12. What do you use to cross-check the taxonomic identification of the reference specimens?

- Cataloge of Life
- WoRMS (World Register of Marine Species)
- GBIF (Global Biodiversity Information Facility)
- [Open answer]
- NCBI taxonomy
- ENA (European Nucleotide Archive)
- UNITE

Q13. Approximately for how many species have you generated reference sequences?

[Open answer]

Q14. Approximately for how many specimens have you generated reference sequences?

[Open answer]

Q15. Do you keep all the reference specimens as vouchers?

- Yes
- No

Q16. If not, or in cases where you kept only some reference specimens as vouchers, why? If the reason(s) is(are) specific to a certain taxa, please specify.

[Open answer]

Q17. If so, what kind of voucher do you keep?

[Open answer]

Q18. In which kind of institution do you keep voucher material?

- Museum and other public institutions
- Academic Institutions
- Personal/Local collections
- [Open answer]

Q19. Please specify the institution where the voucher material is kept.

[Open answer]

Q20. Under what conditions were the reference specimens stored?

- Desiccated
- -20 °C
- -80 °C
- Ethanol
- Formaldehyde
- [Open answer]

Q21. Do you keep stored an aliquot of the extracted DNA from reference specimens for future research?

- Yes
- No

Q22. If not, what is the reason for not storing DNA aliquots from reference specimens?

[Open answer]

Q23. If so, where do you store DNA aliquots from reference specimens?

[Open answer]

Q24. Under what conditions do you keep stored DNA aliquot from reference specimens?

- -20 °C
- -80 °C
- [Open answer]

Q25. For which genetic marker(s) have you generated reference sequences?

- 16S rRNA (SSU)
- 18S rRNA (SSU)
- COX1
- rbcL
- matK
- ITS1-5.8S-ITS2
- Exome
- [Open answer]

Q26. Please, specify to which taxa if different molecular markers were used

[Open answer]

Q27. Have you deposited your generated reference sequences/DNA reference library in a database?

- Yes
- No

Q28. If not, why have you not deposited the reference libraries in a database? Please, specify to which taxa if different molecular markers were used.

[Open answer]

Q29. If so, in which type of database have you deposited the reference sequences?

- Public
- Private/Personal
- Both
- None (only if you answered “No” in the previous question)

Q30. In which database have you deposited the reference sequences? Please specify to each taxa you have mentioned previously if different databases were used.

[Open answer]

Q31. Have you deposited any metadata along with the reference sequences and/or library(ies)?

- Yes
- No

Q32. Which type of metadata did you generate when creating DNA reference sequences?

- Project name/acronym
- Image record
- Geographic coordinates
- Depth/Altitude
- Tissue collected
- Voucher specimen location
- Voucher specimen ID
- Specimen collector

- Specimen identifier
- Environment (ecosystem)
- Environmental data of collection site
- Accompanying species
- Molecular marker (name and abbreviation)
- Sequenced region
- Trace files
- PCR primers
- Sequencing primers
- Barcode generator (who generated sequences)

Survey section III - DNA Reference Library Management

Q33. Do you have a procedure to accept/reject a reference barcode?

- Yes
- No

Q34. If so, could you specify it?

[Open answer]

Q35. Do you have a procedure to curate the taxonomy of the library?

- Yes
- No

Q36. If so, could you describe it?

[Open answer]

Q37. Do you keep (or have you kept) track of the experts that curated the reference library?

- Yes
- No

Q38. Specifically to the reference library(ies) that you generated, is it (or are they) open access?

- Yes
- No

Q39. If not, are there any other types of intellectual property associated with the reference libraries? Please specify.

[Open answer]

Q40. Are (at least some) of these sequences or dataset(s) already published?

- Yes
- No

Q41. If you answered “Yes”, is there a link that you can provide (e.g.: database/website URL, publication DOI, etc)?

[Open answer]

Q43. Do you keep previous versions of the reference library after its curation?

- Yes
- No

Q44. Did you follow a metadata standard?

- Yes
- No

Q45. If so, which?

[Open answer]

Appendix 2. Classification system for the accuracy of specimen's taxonomic identification

Classification system for the accuracy of specimen's taxonomic identification adopted from Ward (2012).

Levels of reliability	Description
1 <i>Highly reliable identification</i>	Specimen identified by: a) an internationally recognised authority of the group, or b) a specialist that is presently studying or has reviewed the group
2 <i>Identification made with a high degree of confidence at all levels</i>	Specimen identified by a trained identifier who had prior knowledge of the group or used available literature to identify the specimen
3 <i>Identification made with high confidence to genus but less so to species</i>	Specimen identified by: a) a trained identifier who was confident of its generic placement but did not substantiate its species identification using the literature b) a trained identifier who used literature but still could not make a positive identification to species, or c) an untrained identifier who used most of the available literature to make the identification
4 <i>Identification made with limited confidence</i>	Specimen identified by: a) a trained identifier who was confident of its family placement but unsure of its generic or species identification (no literature used apart from illustrations), or b) an untrained identifier who had/used limited literature to make the identification
5 <i>Superficial identification</i>	Specimen identified by: a) a trained identifier who is uncertain of the family placement of the species (cataloguing identification only), b) untrained identifier using, at best, figures in a guide, or c) where the status and expertise of the identifier is unknown

Appendix 3. DNA reference databases review (manual)

Data from reviewing DNA reference databases can be accessed via: [Databases](#)

Appendix 4. Dataset developed for retraining Llama2

Dataset developed by several project's members, for retraining Llama2: [Paper content training set - pilot.xlsx](#)

Appendix 5. Database with results from LLM

Database including resulting data from processed papers via LLM: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Gk7EBMkEr0_iJCFXTMzlvukFAKjYwP1G/view?usp=drive_link

Appendix 6. Questionnaire resulting data

Resulting data from the survey can be accessed via: [RefLib_Survey-Data.xlsx](#)

Appendix 7. Target taxa

List of terms used by all the contributors (accepted answers) used to describe the various taxonomic groups here assessed. Some terms were too vague to be considered a more specific

taxonomic group, namely “zooplankton”, “invertebrates”, “benthic invertebrates”, and “macroinvertebrates”, which were all merely included in the metazoan category.

Taxa group	Terms used	Count	Total	
ARCHAEA	Archaea	2	3	
	Archaea (as in prokaryotic plankton)	1		
BACTERIA	Bacteria	2	4	
	Bacteria (as in prokaryotic plankton)	1		
	α -Cyanobacteria	1		
EUKARYA	Eukarya	2	2	
Chromista	Brown algae	1	4	
	Diatoms	2		
	Microalgae	1		
Plantae	Marine plants	1	3	
	Red algae	1		
	Green algae	1		
Metazoa	Chordata	Vertebrates	1	13
		Mammals	1	
		Reptiles	1	
		Fish	10	
	Annelida	Leeches	1	4
Oligochaetes		1		
Polychaete		2		
Arthropoda	Crustacea	3	17	

Taxa group	Terms used	Count	Total
	Malacostraca	1	
	Decapoda	1	
	Pinnotheridae	1	
	Neotanaidae	1	
	Grapsidae	1	
	Peracarids	1	
	Amphipoda	1	
	<i>Gammarus</i>	1	
	<i>Dikerogammarus villosus</i>	1	
Insecta	Insecta	2	
	Diptera	1	
	Ephemeroptera	1	6
	Odonata	1	
	Plecoptera	1	
Arachnida	Mites	1	
	Hydracarina	1	2
Cnidaria	Cnidaria	1	1
Mollusca	Mollusca	4	4
Zooplankton*	Zooplankton	5	5
Invertebrates*	Invertebrates	9	
	Benthic invertebrates	1	12
	Macroinvertebrates	2	
VIRUS	Virus (plankton)	1	1